

Hyperwell: Local-First, Collaborative Notebooks for Digital Annotation

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Abstract

Highlights, scribbling, and marginal notes: Annotation is often a private practice that we only occasionally share with others, or even more rarely share publicly. Once considered fundamental to hypertext systems, the potential of annotating digital documents is often overlooked in today's technology. As data commonly leaves our devices when collaborating, further questions arise on digital ownership and privacy. In this thesis, I examine the question of how both ownership and privacy can be ensured in the context of Digital Humanities research, which increasingly leverages interoperable infrastructures and Linked Open Data.

In an explorative study, I first investigate the aspects of real-time collaboration in research tools, followed by an examination of institutional services on Peer-to-Peer (P2P) networks. By establishing interoperability between such networks and the web, I then propose two approaches for bridging those networks and strengthening privacy, ownership, and private collaboration following the paradigm of local-first software.

I argue that by balancing the autonomy of peers and the determinism of the web, gateways can translate across the separation of both networks while supporting peers by providing archiving and data availability. This enables researchers to perform private and collaborative annotation, while the underlying data can be embedded into existing workflows due to the bridge between both systems. Future work concerns the viability of this approach in scholarly environments and further research on the usability of distributed systems in the academic context.

Acknowledgements

In the following, I will discuss collaboration and peer-to-peer systems. Both of these actually helped me write this thesis and I'd like to thank a few like-minded peers—physical ones, albeit sometimes connected remotely.

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I am also indebted to Bastian Havers-Zulka, Hans Christian Schmitz, and Christofer Meinecke for their substantial feedback on my writing. The logo of Hyperwell, an asterism scanned from a 1922 edition of James Joyce's *Ulysses*, emerged from discussions with Lucas Dino Nolte, who is the best typomaniac that I know.

Much of this work is due to the emotional support of Elisa Hartmann; her loving critique and harsh encouragement. She had my back in times where I did nothing but sit and write, something I likely won't ever be able to make up for. Finally, I want to thank my family for their unwavering trust, comfort, and support.

List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CRDT	Conflict-free Rreplicated Data Ttype
CTS	Canonical Text Services
DH	Digital Humanities
DHT	Distributed Hash Table
DNS	Domain Name System
DOM	Document Object Model
IIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LAN	Local Area Network
LD	Linked Data
LDP	Linked Data Platform
LOD	Linked Open Data
NAT	Network Address Translation
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
REST	Representational State Transfer
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SDK	Software Development Kit
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TTL	Time To Live
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
uTP	uTorrent Transport Protocol
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Ideas on hypertext emerged from the work of digital researchers as early as the 1960s, originally describing the need for expressing non-sequential patterns of thought in writing. Ted Nelson described this with the *intertwining* of knowledge:

EVERYTHING IS DEEPLY INTERTWINGLED. In an important sense there are no “subjects” at all; there is only all knowledge, since the cross-connections among the myriad topics of this world simply cannot be divided up neatly. (Nelson 1987, DM 45)

To express non-linearity, researchers and developers of hypertext systems adopted the notion of hyperlinks, which would express semantic relations between documents and could be used for hypertext fiction² and cohesive scientific documentation (Berners-Lee 1989). The ubiquitous <a> element of the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML), conceived by Berners-Lee and Connolly (1995), realizes such relations on today’s World Wide Web. It lacks further modalities for articulating non-linearity, however, when compared to Ted Nelson’s *Xanadu* hypertext system (Voß 2019). With *transclusion* (i.e., including parts of one document within another), documents on Xanadu could be composed of a multitude of smaller documents by referencing rather than copying their contents. Transclusion references work by granularly specifying parts of a resource, such as a piece of text. Consequently, other forms exist to express non-sequential

2. Hypertext fiction uses hyperlinks for expressing nonlinearity in literature. Many popular works of hypertext fiction have been published by Eastgate: <http://eastgate.com/>.

thought as described by Nelson, for instance annotations and footnotes.

Marshall (1997) explored the analog modalities of hypertext when analyzing students' annotations on used books. Commonly despised by librarians and collectors alike, annotation on paper makes for a great way of connecting related knowledge and thoughts in situ to the underlying source. The physical manifestation of text in books obviously causes an inherited limitation when making annotations on paper, such as too little space for marginal notes. The digital medium lifts those restrictions; almost encouragingly, annotating digital text is just a matter of switching bits from zero to one and vice versa, enabling real-time collaborative note-taking or intensive public commentary. These prospects could extend the functionalities of interactive reading environments and digital libraries, connecting derived knowledge with its sources.

However, applications tend to support the two extremes of annotation: private and personal (any note-taking app), or public and collaborative (e.g., Hypothes.is³). A third modality of annotation that resides between these two—I will call it *private collaboration*—is still missing in most annotation environments. While public collaboration generally does not impose any level of privacy, the sensitivity of private collaboration makes it difficult to realize such exclusive communication channels. Nonetheless, private collaboration allows for many kinds of day-to-day interactions between people despite their geographical distance.

Be it musings in private diary entries or highlights of favorite verses on a shared copy of Goethe's *Die Leiden des jungen Werthers*, even today, little attention is paid towards the private aspects of digital notes. Web-backed services, for example, rarely impose end-to-end encryption between their users' devices. This is even more important for private collaboration, where data is commonly routed along a myriad of intermediaries on the network before reaching the computers of collaborators. Digital notebooks must ensure privacy and security, and the web has yet to prove itself capable of treating annotations accordingly.

3. <https://web.hypothes.is/>.

1.1 Motivation: A Question of Ownership

Ever since its birth in the early 1990s, the web has been a facilitator of economic growth. The dot-com bubble of the early 2000s and the rise of Silicon Valley during the 2010s were founded on the sudden possibilities of near-instant, worldwide communication (and the vast availability of venture capital). The subsequent commercialization of the web nevertheless entailed threats to its fundamental principles. An increasing amount of data is stored in the *cloud*—a ubiquitous, mysterious entity—with few prospects on ownership and privacy. As Kleppmann et al. put it:

Although they let you access your data anywhere, all data access must go via the server, and you can only do the things that the server will let you do. In a sense, you don't have full ownership of that data – the cloud provider does. In the words of a bumper sticker: "There is no cloud, it's just someone else's computer." (Kleppmann et al. 2019, p. 155)

Arguably, there exists a difference between *practical* and *theoretical* ownership of data. Practically, I possess data while it remains on my computer. However, data is often distributed to third-party services for backup or collaboration. If data is stored on the cloud, I could ask customer support to send me all the data I have provided them with, yet in the meantime I would need to somehow validate my ownership remotely. I can then prove my theoretical ownership of data by cryptographic means: signing or encrypting data with cryptographic keys allows me to mathematically verify the signature or even prevent third parties from accessing the data.

That said, the question of ownership in regard to data availability on a personally owned device remains. Peer-to-Peer (P2P) systems commonly address this issue by establishing communication channels directly between two parties with no intermediaries involved (except for relaying data). Initially popularized among file-sharing services of the early 2000s, such as Napster, applications nowadays increasingly leverage P2P principles to eliminate the need for third parties and central authorities in their systems. Blockchain technology and Decentralized Autonomous Organizations (DAOs) incentivize this development by lobbying for free and global trade.

Whether motivated by crypto-economic aspects or not, decentralized appli-

cations demand new technological frameworks and the revisiting of usability concerns. With *local-first software*, Kleppmann et al. (2019) introduced a manifesto for applications that store data locally, do not depend on network connections, and yet—once connected—enable secure real-time collaboration with peers. By featuring both practical and theoretical ownership, users can maintain their data locally while distributing cryptographically-signed changes to collaborators. Could this serve as a foundation for reimagining hypertext annotation?

1.2 Research Goals and Affiliated Work

The initial research question for this thesis emerged out of a personal frustration about the current state of platform-centric tools affecting the modalities of annotation on the web. Arguably, P2P systems have their downsides, which I will outline later in this thesis. Last year, I had the opportunity to join various academic gatherings, one of which was the ACM Hypertext Conference in Hof, Germany. This allowed me to discuss digital annotation with scholars of Digital Humanities and Computer Science alike. Some scholars approved my concerns on digital ownership, others objected to the use of P2P systems and less authoritative control. After all, large-scale projects can quickly impose hierarchical structures, especially when public funding and oversight is involved. This led me to pose research questions on the actual *feasibility* of such systems by exploring benefits for digital scholarly workflows:

1. How do users perceive collaborative workflows on digital annotation in contemporary Digital Humanities tools?
2. How can personal ownership and institutional governance be considered in a P2P architecture with distributed governance?
3. How could a system be realized technically with such considerations?

Throughout the project, I had the opportunity to talk and write publicly about the main contribution of this thesis: an architecture for distributed digital annotation called *Hyperwell*. First, I gave a talk titled *From Me to You: Peer-to-Peer Collaboration with Linked Data* at the second DARIAH Digital Humanities workshop at the University of Neuchâtel, Switzerland. A short paper about the Hyperwell architecture (co-authored by my thesis supervisor, Dr. Thomas Köntges) was published

in the workshop proceedings (Kabel and Köntges 2020) as an open publication on the newly released DARIAH Campus⁴ website.

Second, Chiara Palladino (Furman University) and I are preparing a joint open publication on using Recogito—an open annotation environment—for collaborative learning in classrooms. The results of the study described in chapter 3 yielded not only feedback on collaborative annotation in general, but also on how students could collaborate with digital tools in classrooms. This forthcoming open publication and an accompanying post on the Pelagios blog⁵ set out to provide educators with insights on how (digital) classes could be improved by using collaborative environments such as Recogito.

In order to build Hyperwell, I have sketched user interfaces using graphics tools and created prototypical implementations. The centerpiece of Hyperwell is a gateway server that bridges the P2P network into the web. While the official print version of this thesis contains all affiliated code repositories, I have decided to openly publish the gateway server (Kabel 2020b). Further affiliated software is available on the Hyperwell project’s page on GitHub.⁶

1.3 Synopsis

This thesis is aimed at readers with an affinity for computer technology, but not *necessarily* computer scientists. The given subject concerns collaborative workflows and digital ownership questions alike, with far-ranging prospects on how we can improve our treatment of scholarly annotation in Digital Humanities and beyond. Therefore, the proposed solutions heavily depend on feedback and insights from the scientific community. I successively introduce the related topics—collaborative workflows, Linked Data, and P2P networks—throughout chapters 2 to 4, followed by details on the actual implementation.

Following this introduction, chapter 2 contains a discussion of related work that concerns hypertext, digital annotation, Linked Data, P2P applications, and research infrastructure in Digital Humanities. Mostly focusing on scholarly research, throughout that chapter I will cover fundamental and academically doc-

4. <https://campus.dariah.eu/>.

5. <https://medium.com/pelagios>.

6. <https://github.com/hyperwell>.

umented technology that is used in this thesis. I will state further technological decisions in footnotes in later parts of this thesis.

In chapter 3, I will present a study on collaborative annotation workflows in Digital Humanities. Arguing for a shift in personal data ownership, particularly on annotation, I will discuss aspects of governance in decentralized and distributed systems in chapter 4. For a sustainable, ownership-preserving separation of personal and public data on P2P systems, I introduce the notions of digital notebooks and public entities.

Chapter 5 concerns the technical work of the thesis. I will present two designs and their respective implementations of an architecture for decentralized, collaborative annotation, called Hyperwell. I will then discuss observations, issues, and shortcomings in chapter 6. Chapter 7 will then revisit the contributions of this thesis and sketch future work.

In parts of this thesis (mostly in chapters 4 and 5), I will use technical vocabulary and related terminology. Many of the acronyms used—*P2P*, *DHT*, *TCP*—describe concepts and technology related to computer networks. While I will briefly explain such terms as I progress, readers may find it helpful to consult the list of abbreviations in the front matter of this thesis.

Chapter 2

Related Work

In the following, I will outline the background of this thesis in a brief review of related literature and projects, covering this work’s research goals of *feasibility*, *usability*, and *interoperability* of a decentralized annotation system. As opposed to the later section 4, in this chapter I attempt to draw a cohesive, non-judgmental picture of related work. The discussed works are *intertwined*⁷ to a certain degree, but I will try to cover them in chronological order.

The literature background includes development of hypertext systems and the world-wide web, digital libraries, and digital annotation in section 2.1 and the contemporary development of real-time collaborative web applications in section 2.2. In section 2.3, I will highlight the prospects of Linked Data and its impact on Digital Humanities, followed by a brief discussion of fundamental peer-to-peer technology and file-sharing systems in section 2.4. Finally, in section 2.5 I connect the earlier aspects of real-time collaboration, hypertext, and decentralization, in order to outline a recent development known as *local-first applications*.

2.1 Hypertext and Annotation

Influenced by early works on interactive knowledge processing such as Vannevar Bush’s *Memex*, the concept of hypertext has initially been shaped by Nelson in 1965:

7. Nelson coined this term in his 1974 book, “*Computer Lib/Dream Machines*”, in order to describe the complex relations of human knowledge.

[Hypertext] mean[s] a body of written or pictorial material interconnected in such a complex way that it could not conveniently be presented or represented on paper. It may contain summaries, or maps of its contents and their interrelations; it may contain annotations, additions and footnotes from scholars who have examined it. (Nelson 1965, p. 96)

Particularly relations between documents known as *hyperlinks* became popular among hypertext pioneers, enabling writers and readers alike to explore text in a non-sequential way. In “*Literary Machines*”—a print publication that has actually been designed as hypertext—Nelson sketches a system called *Xanadu* that goes even further and processes chunks of digital texts into entire documents, backed by a network of servers for managing these units (figure 2.1). Called *transclusion*, the resulting documents would be composed of the aforementioned chunks, and documents as well as chunks themselves were to be stored with each their editing history, something Nelson called “an evolving ongoing braid” (Nelson 1993, 2/14f). Furthermore, document servers would manage documents by storing their entire history on disk.

Figure 2.1: Documents created by transclusion from xanalogical storage in Xanadu (Nelson 1993, 0/6). The transcluded units can be standalone pieces of text or digital media and have links in between them.

While there had been progress on a multitude of hypertext systems⁸, the World Wide Web (WWW), invented by Tim Berners-Lee, became what we today commonly refer to as the *web* (Berners-Lee 1989). Originally designed to serve documents within the CERN institution, Berners-Lee subsequently created a dedicated protocol, Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP, Fielding et al. 1999), and a specialized, hypertext-capable markup language, the Hypertext Markup Language (HTML, Berners-Lee and Connolly 1995).

With the advent of world-scale hypertext systems as well as technological advances in the digitization of physical documents, the first digital libraries emerged. One such library, the Perseus Digital Library, founded by the Perseus Project, spans a vast collection of structured texts, translations, and dictionaries (Smith, Rydberg-Cox, and Crane 2000). Not limited to the physical appearance of resources, digital libraries can utilize tools for Natural Language Processing (NLP) and provide readers with contextual information. Furthermore, these digital collections of text suggest opportunities for digital annotation, since bodies of annotations can be virtually related to the source and thus create a publicly-accessible collection of derived semantic knowledge. Marshall predicted such prospects in her pioneering work and analyzed over 150 pre-owned student books that have been shared and annotated by various generations of students (Marshall 1997). She categorized the observed annotations—e.g., underlining, high-level highlighting, marginal notes—into six functional categories—e.g., aiding memory and interpretation—pictured in figure 2.2. In a follow-up publication, Marshall gives an outlook of how these observations could be applied to annotation of hypertext.

Resources on the web are usually identified by Uniform Resource Locators (URL); for example, the URL `https://www.ccc.de/de/support` refers to a resource of path `/de/support` that resides on the host behind `www.ccc.de`. URLs, however, do not support *canonical referencing*, i.e., identifying resources independently across systems. This can hinder workflows in digital libraries and academia, which demand elaborate referencing mechanisms.

Alternative identification schemes such as Digital Object Identifiers⁹ (DOIs) allow end-to-end persistent referencing. Thereby, references to particular versions of a document with each their own DOI can be resolved independently of network

8. Jakob Voß prepared an interactive visualization of the timeline of hypertext, backend by structured knowledge on Wikidata: <http://jakobvoss.de/hypertext-timeline/>.

9. <https://www.doi.org/>.

Form	Function
Underlining or highlighting higher level structure (like section headings); telegraphic marginal symbols like asterisks; crossouts.	Procedural signaling for future attention.
Short highlightings; circled words or phrases; other within-text markings; marginal markings like asterisks.	Placemarking and aiding memory.
Appropriate notation in margins or near figures or equations.	Problem-working.
Short notes in the margins; longer notes in other textual interstices; words or phrases between lines of text.	Interpretation.
Extended highlighting or underlining.	Tracing progress through difficult narrative.
Notes, doodlings, drawings, and other such markings unrelated to the materials themselves.	Incidental reflection of the material circumstances of reading.

Figure 2.2: Analysis of various types of annotation curated by Marshall (1997).

hosts. The Canonical Text Service (CTS¹⁰) system continues even further and provides a scheme for referencing individual passages of text (Koentges et al., [forthcoming](#)). Originally developed for use with classic texts, CTS allows to reference passages of a work independently of its medium. Other distributed systems, such as Git and IPFS, commonly leverage content addressing mechanisms as I will detail later in this chapter.

2.2 Digital Real-Time Collaboration

Further advances in digital technology and, particularly, in real-time data communication via mobile networks and increased internet bandwidth, offer further prospects of real-time collaborative work done digitally. In 1992, Dourish and Bellotti already derived requirements for shared digital workspaces from studies on remote work. Complementing the necessity of real-time *communication* for participants (such as a voice call), they state that applications realizing real-time *collaboration* in shared workspaces should also exchange information on the underlying digital sources and tools (Dourish and Bellotti 1992). To synchronize the current progress of others' work, user interfaces should carefully shift users' awareness by visually emphasizing changes made by others, a concept they call *shared feedback*.

It wasn't until the next century, however, that such collaboration could be

10. <http://cts.informatik.uni-leipzig.de/>.

realized on the web. Initially, the web platform relied solely on HTTP for transmitting data between clients and servers. HTTP could indeed be *abused* for real-time communication (Fette and Melnikov 2011, p. 4), which resulted in an unwanted overhead due to the ephemerality of the protocol: the underlying Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) connections are usually closed after HTTP request-response exchanges. Shared workspaces, however, as emphasized by Dourish and Bellotti, demand bidirectional communication. The web platform meanwhile specified two such bidirectional, real-time communication protocols that are commonly supported in today's web browsers: the WebSocket protocol and WebRTC.

The WebSocket protocol was designed as a simple solution to the aforementioned lack of continuous, bidirectional communication on the web. By using existing HTTP connections established via TCP, and subsequently *upgrading* them to persistent WebSocket connections, both server and client can transmit data to either side (p. 5ff). The Web Real-Time Communication protocol (WebRTC) continues to establish persistent and secure connections not just between client and server, but rather as a peer-to-peer (P2P) protocol between all kinds of devices (Jennings, Boström, and Bruaroey 2019). WebRTC requires a handshaking mechanism via a trusted third party—a signaling service—in order to exchange connection information called Interactive Connectivity Establishment (ICE). To mitigate common issues of personal devices connected via Network Address Translation (NAT) or firewalls, WebRTC relies on further technology for externally relaying traffic.

The widespread support for such technologies in current web browsers sparked a wave of web-based applications that offer spaces for real-time collaborative work. In the following list the reader will find a selection of such tools that are arguably among the most used:

- Google Docs¹¹, an online, collaborative word processor with elaborate support for annotation and editing.
- Trello¹², a collaborative project management tool that allows to assign and move tasks across different boards (i.e., domains).
- Figma¹³, a vector-based design tool for creating and testing user interface designs. Figma allows collaboration by synchronizing the canvas with par-

11. <https://docs.google.com/>.

12. <https://trello.com/>.

13. <https://figma.com/>.

- participants in real-time, as well as their cursor movements.
- Notion¹⁴, an online knowledge management tool. Similar to a Wiki, Notion allows users to create pages composed of building blocks such as text and multimedia. Notion shows real-time activity of other users by synchronizing as their focus moves between each such block.

2.3 Linked Data and Digital Humanities

Digital Humanities—an inherently digital discipline—concerns various interdisciplinary fields of research such as digital archeology, digital history, and digital classics. Hence, the landscape of tools and infrastructure in Digital Humanities research is vast and yet lacks a coherent overview. Initiatives such as the EU-funded DARIAH¹⁵ attempt to improve literacy with digital tools and provide a dedicated infrastructure available to a pan-European audience of research groups.

Due to its interdisciplinary, communities in Digital Humanities frequently depend on remote collaboration, Hunyadi (2016) notes. Using software for real-time video conferencing, researchers quickly established video-based plenary talks and virtual conferences. Scholarly collaboration continues with shared digital infrastructures among labs and projects. By embracing best-practices guidelines on research data management such as the FAIR principles¹⁶, initiatives promote sustainable workflows for handling digital assets among scholars: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of research data all shall ensure that data measured, processed, and evaluated in research is properly managed (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Linked Open Data (LOD) could meet such requirements. While HTML provides elements for semantically tagging content, such as titles, descriptions, and marginal notes, it lacks ways of describing *pure* data without markup. Linked Data (LD) and, more generally, the Semantic Web, attempts to bring a semantic framework to data. The LD stack is built upon established web technologies, such as HTTP and URLs, and imposes semantic relations via triples modeled after the Resource Description Framework (RDF). With RDF triples, an external party can express the semantic relation between two entities by specifying a *sub-*

14. <https://notion.so/>.

15. <https://www.dariah.eu/>.

16. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

ject, a *predicate*, and an *object*¹⁷ (Bizer, Heath, and Berners-Lee 2009). Linked Open Data continues even further and makes Linked Data publicly accessible.

With the Solid project¹⁸, a group led by Berners-Lee conceived an architecture for managing personal data separately from applications and services on the web with online storage services called *pubs* (Mansour et al. 2016). Solid introduces Linked Data Platforms (LDPs), which are services that exclusively manage Linked Data containers—i.e., semantic collections of LD items—and their related media assets. Furthermore, LDPs specify how clients can interact with the stored data via REST-based APIs¹⁹.

LOD can play a crucial role in the realization of FAIR in regard to data repositories in Digital Humanities. Since LOD is publicly accessible, researchers can prepare collections of data accordingly and publish them via HTTP, each with their own URI for distinctly referencing them on the web. Shared online gazetteers, for example, provide collections of LD-formatted places that can be semantically related onto other resources, such as ancient maps and classic texts (Simon et al. 2017).

The Web Annotation specification emerged from the persistent lack of standardized annotation on the web and builds upon the previously defined concepts of LOD and LDPs (Sanderson, Ciccarese, and Van de Sompel 2013). The specification consists of two components: First, the Web Annotation Data Model, in which annotations are expressed using the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), or more precisely the JSON-LD schema for use in LD environments. Following a versatile ontology similar to the observations from Marshall, an annotation fundamentally consists of three properties, as pictured in listing 2.1:

- The annotation's *identifier*, which is a web resource specified via its Internationalized Uniform Identifier (IRI, similar to an URI).
- Its *target*, which is a web resource, also specified via its IRI.
- An annotation *body*, which again can be a web resource. Alternatively, as done in listing 2.1, the body can be provided as an inlined JSON object. For

17. In RDF, objects are identified by their URIs. In an example given by Bizer, Heath, and Berners-Lee, a subject (<http://dig.csail.mit.edu/data#DIG>) relates via a predicate (<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/member>) to an object (<http://www.w3.org/People/Berners-Lee/card#i>).

18. Although started by Berners-Lee at MIT, the Solid project is now managed by an affiliated commercial startup called Inrupt: <https://solidproject.org/>.

19. API is an acronym for Application Programming Interface. With APIs that adhere to Representational State Transfer (REST), applications can execute common actions such as creating, retrieving, and editing data via HTTP.

Listing 2.1 An example annotation in form of a JSON-LD-based Web Annotation, as pictured by the Web Annotation data model technical report (Sanderson, Ciccarese, and Young 2017). This annotation adds a textual annotation containing the text *j'adore !* to a web resource.

```
{
  "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/anno.jsonld",
  "id": "http://example.org/anno5",
  "type": "Annotation",
  "body": {
    "type": "TextualBody",
    "value": "<p>j'adore !</p>",
    "format": "text/html",
    "language": "fr"
  },
  "target": "http://example.org/photo1"
}
```

expressing a specific portion of the target resource—e.g., a piece of text, or a section of an image—a wide range of standardized *fragment selectors* can be used.

The Web Annotation Protocol, as the second component, defines the Application Programming Interface (API) of an annotation server and thus, how client applications can transmit Web Annotations via HTTP. The API identifies annotations by their IRI²⁰ and consists of four basic verbs known from REST-based APIs: Clients can retrieve annotations (GET), create annotations (POST), update annotations (PUT), and delete annotations (DELETE). These actions can be executed on collections of annotations—semantic groups of items called *containers* on the LDP—or the respective annotation, referred to by each their respective IRI.

With Dokieli²¹, Capadisli et al. created a publishing environment that supports storing documents on loosely-connected data stores—i.e., documents created on Dokieli are not necessarily tied to it. By adhering to a multitude of LD protocols and supporting the LDP, Dokieli is compliant with the aforementioned Solid architecture and attempts to support a separation between data stores and the respective applications operating on these stores. Furthermore, Dokieli provides social interactions such as *liking* sections of text and commenting by leveraging

20. An example IRI would be: <https://www.example.com/container-name/annotation-id>.

21. <https://dokie.li/>.

the Web Annotation protocol and data model.

Figure 2.3: Annotating an ancient map on Recogito. Recogito allows users to annotate sources, establish semantic relations—e.g., referencing places or people—and share these collections with other users.

The capabilities of Web Annotation are not limited to social interactions on text. Initiated by the Pelagios project²², Recogito is a platform that has been created purposely for *semantic* annotation (Simon et al. 2017). In order to provide semantic annotation, Recogito leverages LD principles and allows to semantically tag portions of a source with LD collections, such as the aforementioned gazetteers or historic individuals. Besides text, Recogito also supports annotating static images and canonical resources, such as documents identified by CTS URNs or large-scale image galleries via the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF).

22. <https://pelagios.org/>.

2.4 Peer-to-Peer Networks

The earliest concepts of hypertext established client-server architectures for storing hypertext documents distributed among an array of hypertext servers (Nelson 1993; Berners-Lee 1989). These architectures, as opposed to a monolithic structure, allow the web to be decentralized and collaborative. Yet data on the web tends to gather in silos on a minority of servers, threatening the decentralized nature of the web (Capadisli et al. 2017). Federated systems significantly emphasize decentralization by ensuring interoperability between multiple servers participating in the same network and thus composing one distributed system.

Esguerra surveys such federated *social* networks, motivated by issues on privacy and censorship of large-scale social networks such as Facebook and Twitter: “Federated social networks [...] are a vital step towards fulfilling values often lacking in the existing social networking ecosystem: user-control, diversity of services, innovation, and more” (Esguerra 2011). The federated social network Diaspora²³ has been an early attempt at building such a system. Building on the Diaspora network’s success, Mastodon²⁴ became increasingly popular in recent months with about 3.9 Million users across about 2,600 instances as of today²⁵. By implementing the standardized ActivityPub protocol (Webber et al. 2018), applications such as Mastodon leverage semantic LD principles and advance interoperability even further. Similar to the LDP, ActivityPub specifies server-to-server interactions with semantically tagged data.

Figure 2.4 pictures three different layouts for communication networks with each node of the network connected to others by distinctive strategies (Baran 1964). Centralized networks, as shown on the leftmost diagram, promote a single node to govern all other nodes which can render efficient systems, albeit bearing a single point of failure due to singular authority. Decentralized networks divide centralized power into a multitude of nodes, commonly called *supernodes*. The web, as mentioned above, has been designed with a decentralized architecture where web servers function as supernodes. Instead of connecting to a single node for all their needs, clients on the web connect to a variety of servers via their Internet Protocol (IP) addresses. Federated systems emphasize server-to-server commu-

23. <https://diasporafoundation.org/>.

24. <https://joinmastodon.org/>.

25. The fediverse.network website provides various usage and network statistics on federated systems such as Mastodon, PeerTube, and WordPress: <https://fediverse.network/mastodon>. The statistics mentioned on Mastodon were current as of April 8, 2020.

Figure 2.4: Architectures of communication networks (Baran 1964). In a centralized network, a single node has authority over all other nodes. Decentralized systems introduce supernodes as opposed to a single authority. Distributed or P2P networks diminish the notion of supernodes and introduce a fully distributed governance.

nication for interoperability, pictured as connections between supernodes in the center diagram of figure 2.4.

In distributed networks, shown on the rightmost diagram, resources are distributed equally among peers. However, fully decentralizing power of a complex system can pose substantial challenges: How can nodes on the network determine where they may request a particular piece of data from? How can nodes verify that the data they received has not been manipulated by a malicious actor? How can a node prevent others from changing a read-only piece of data? The technologies I will introduce in the following attempt to address some of these challenges.

Distributed Hash Tables (DHTs) attempt to solve the issue of discoverability and can be propagated *within* a distributed network or managed externally as an *overlay network*. A DHT stores connection information for nodes in a hash table that is distributed among nodes—as opposed to a more centralized solution like Domain Name System (DNS) commonly used on the web. Since the hash table is dis-

tributed, nodes may need multiple hops—i.e., connecting to a multitude of nodes for obtaining the required parts of the DHT—in order to resolve the data of a particular node (Maymounkov and Mazières 2002). The amount of hops needed for retrieving information on particular nodes defines the distance between nodes and thus the efficiency of a DHT.

Figure 2.5: Binary tree of a Kademlia DHT (Maymounkov and Mazières 2002). Nodes are sorted within the tree by each ID, a 160-bit number. In order to discover other nodes in other subtrees of the DHT, a node (black dot with ID 0011 . . .) needs to have contact with nodes of the other subtrees (gray ovals).

One such DHT is Kademlia (Maymounkov and Mazières 2002), pictured in figure 2.5. A Kademlia-type DHT manages nodes of a network in a binary tree, sorted by their respective ID, which is a 160-bit number. These binary trees are divided into subtrees, and each subtree’s nodes maintain connection information on each other. With this binary subtree separation, the Kademlia DHT defines the distance between peers as an XOR metric based on their ID, i.e., the more different two nodes’ IDs are in terms of their bit representation, the more distant they become. For use in BitTorrent, Loewenstern and Norberg developed a DHT based on Kademlia that contains extensions related to torrents—i.e., distributed archives on BitTorrent—and the BitTorrent protocol (Loewenstern and Norberg 2020).

An append-only log is a list-based data structure that exclusively allows the addition of entries: “A log is perhaps the simplest possible storage abstraction. It is an append-only, totally-ordered sequence of records ordered by time” (Kreps 2013). Nelson previously described such a log for managing document histories on Xanadu (Nelson 1993, 2/15). Popularized by stream processing frameworks

such as Apache Kafka²⁶ and Apache Samza²⁷, as well as by collaborative systems such as the Git version control system, append-only logs treat the current state of a database as a chronological sequence of changes rather than a definite state. Append-only logs provide a particularly interesting prospect for their distribution, as malicious actors are not able to simply modify the history of a log. Furthermore, entries of a log reference to each other via their content—i.e., content-addressing via hashes—and thus, if an actor of a distributed system mutates an existing entry, all following entries' hashes will change subsequently and the log will break.

Such technologies are commonly utilized in file-sharing systems, with both Gnutella (Chawathe et al. 2003) and BitTorrent (Legout et al. 2007) being well-known contenders that have been frequently researched. Such systems emerged during the popularity of P2P applications in the early 2000s and were commonly used for sharing copyrighted content (Gearlog 2010). Contemporary approaches rather emphasize the development of decentralized applications for bypassing censorship, enabling end-to-end encryption, or facilitating real-time collaboration in day-to-day use cases. IPFS builds on top of the libp2p²⁸ library and creates a world-wide, distributed, and secure file system based on content-addressing (Benet 2014). Dat is a data-sharing protocol actively developed by the Dat Protocol foundation for use in civic and research technology (Robinson et al. 2018). By leveraging a modularized technology stack implemented in JavaScript—such as the Hypercore²⁹ append-only log and the Hyperswarm³⁰ networking stack—Dat can be used in decentralized applications on the web and on the desktop alike. Secure Scuttlebutt (SSB) is a decentralized social network that uses a *gossip* protocol under the assumption that by continuously broadcasting messages on the network, all peers will eventually obtain a consistent state (Tarr et al. 2019).

26. <https://kafka.apache.org/>.

27. <https://samza.apache.org/>.

28. libp2p provides a modular stack for building decentralized applications: <https://libp2p.io/>.

29. <https://github.com/mafintosh/hypercore>.

30. <https://github.com/hyperswarm/hyperswarm>.

2.5 Local-First Applications

In 2019, Kleppmann et al. coined the term *local-first applications*. In a paper called “Local-First Software: You Own Your Data, in Spite of the Cloud,” the authors propose a set of requirements for a novel type of application that overcomes common issues of contemporary real-time collaboration software (Kleppmann et al. 2019): As businesses increasingly rely on cloud providers to manage and provision their technical infrastructure, fewer applications continue to work when not connected to the internet or—even more severe—the company ceases to support the product. Most profoundly, local-first applications expect *all* respective data to be stored locally, which could be text documents or structured databases. By cherishing local data, operations on these data stores happen with lower latency and network connections become optional. Real-time updates are being transmitted nevertheless once back online and are continuously reflected on the user interface.

Issues commonly arise when two users change the same property on a piece of data: If two people were to edit a paragraph of text collaboratively in the same shared document and edited the same word at the same time before synchronizing, this situation would cause a conflict. A centralized authority can occasionally solve such conflicts by applying particular sets of rules for conflict resolution. However, even authoritative entities—e.g., backend servers of some of the collaborative products listed above in section 2.2—frequently fail at automatic merging, resulting in manual conflict resolution and potential data loss for users (Kleppmann et al. 2019).

For use in such environments with frequent changes and conflicts as well as no authoritative merging entity, Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) impose a set of strategies on how to merge various data structures, such as grow-only sets and increment-only integer counters. Extensively documented by Shapiro et al., CRDTs utilize the assumption of Strong Eventual Consistency (SEC) to guarantee that after all peers exchange their operations and individually apply the same merging strategies on each their state, eventually all individual data converges to the same state (Shapiro et al. 2011). Due to their flexibility, CRDTs can be applied to a variety of circumstances, such as distributed collaborative systems. Thus, as CRDTs gained popularity among developers for building applications with offline capabilities and non-authoritative merging, implementations for various platforms and programming environments emerged in research and devel-

opment communities³¹. Kleppmann and Beresford transferred the capabilities of CRDTs to JSON data structures, as JSON objects consist—besides atomic types—of maps and lists, both of which can be commonly merged using CRDT strategies (Kleppmann and Beresford 2017). With Automerge³², they have released a JavaScript-based CRDT that builds upon this research and runs in today’s web browsers (Kleppmann and Beresford 2018).

Building upon Automerge, Kleppmann et al. created a library called *Hypermerge*³³ that integrates conflict-free merging with some of the aforementioned contemporary P2P approaches. Hypermerge documents are identified by their URL (e.g., `hypermerge:/abc123`), which resolves to the underlying distributed data structure. Hypermerge leverages the Dat project’s Hypercore append-only log, which enables storing Automerge changes in chronological order as they occur over time and provides a streaming-based replication mechanism. Hypercore provides additional support exchanging ephemeral messages with peers related to the same log and uses the Noise protocol³⁴, a novel communication protocol with advanced cryptographic privacy features. The Hyperswarm decentralized network and DHT then allows peers to discover each other and subsequently replicate their Hypercore logs of the same document (Frazee 2018).

In a follow-up publication, Hardenberg and Kleppmann detail the implementation of a proof-of-concept, local-first application called *PushPin* that leverages the Hypermerge library as foundation for the application’s data storage. This enables PushPin to operate when offline, yet providing real-time collaboration when online and sharing workspaces with others. Several takeaways emerged from their work, including the benefits of Functional Reactive Programming (FRP) for user interfaces displaying frequent real-time updates as well as ongoing issues around privacy, security, and usability of local-first applications (Hardenberg and Kleppmann 2020).

31. The `crdt.tech` website curates lists of various CRDT implementations complemented by related research papers and a brief documentation around CRDTs: <https://crdt.tech/>.

32. <https://github.com/automerge/>.

33. <https://github.com/automerge/hypermerge>.

34. <https://noiseprotocol.org/>

Chapter 3

Study: Exploring Collaborative Workflows

Clearly, mainstream achievements in the development and engineering of computers led to what we know today as Digital Humanities. Arguably, the increase in computational power resulted in Humanities Computing—computational approaches for Humanities—as well as a general digital practice. Yet the capabilities of computers are not limited by these terms as devices are connected via vast digital networks. Not limited to a mere exchange of discrete information, contemporary computer networks even allow for real-time synchronization of virtual spaces.

One modality of such a virtual space is video conferencing. As Hunyadi (2016) notes, scheduling meetings online—with local and remote colleagues alike—has had an enormous impact on interdisciplinary collaboration in Digital Humanities. In some academic Digital Humanities communities, video conferencing facilitated organizing international events and local plenary discussions alike with little effort to great effect: students could interact with internationally acclaimed researchers while regular remote meetings quickly emerged.

Remote collaboration is not limited to video conferencing. Workplaces can be understood as a curation of tools for particular tasks of work, be it physical or virtual. Video conferencing, however, does not facilitate the collaborative use of actual tools. By transmitting changes on a collaborative piece of work including the state of the tools used, colleagues can collaborate in a shared workspace (Dourish and Bellotti 1992; Schwartz et al. 1998). Tang (1991) outlines the modalities

of a collectively shared workspace in a patent that describes the synchronization capabilities of an application shared among multiple remote screens. Focusing on requirements for remote environments, Dourish and Bellotti (1992) highlight further characteristics of shared workspaces that are being remotely accessed by colleagues. The introduced concept of *shared feedback* suggests shifting users' awareness towards actions executed by others on the underlying workspace. With positive feedback on meetings held remotely in academia, this leaves us with many prospects for real-time collaborative environments. Particularly the collaborative aspects and accessibility of local-first applications make realizing such environments approachable.

Developing a novel annotation environment would have extended the scope of this thesis. Instead, I have chosen to find an existing environment for learning about users' habits when collaborating with digital tools. Arbitrary design choices in the UI should be a minor factor. Already established environments commonly raised feedback from their users and adjusted its user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) accordingly. Among various candidates such as Hypothes.is³⁵ and the Mirador IIIF viewer,³⁶ I elected the Recogito annotation software for the setting of this study. Recogito met the following requirements:

- **Technical and academic documentation:** The Recogito team published their development process (Simon et al. 2017). The source code of Recogito is available publicly.³⁷ The UI of Recogito is extensible and written in JavaScript for use within web browsers. While the Pelagios network maintains an official instance of Recogito³⁸, Recogito supports to run an individual instance within the Docker³⁹ container virtualization environment. Additionally, the team behind Recogito was responsive and supported me while setting up the individual instance.
- **Interoperability with Web Annotation:** While Recogito does not support external annotation storage, its annotation data model is *partially* compliant with the Web Annotation data model.
- **Collaborative workflows:** On Recogito, resources can be shared with other users, allowing for collaborative annotation. I will discuss the modalities of

35. <https://web.hypothes.is/>.

36. <https://projectmirador.org/>.

37. <https://github.com/pelagios/recogito2>.

38. <https://recogito.pelagios.org/>.

39. <https://www.docker.com/>.

collaboration on Recogito in the following.

- **Annotation capabilities:** Recogito offers an environment for annotating textual resources, including classic Greek or Latin texts, and annotating images. Furthermore, users can import canonical resources from CTS repositories and IIF manifests. With a focus on georeferencing, Recogito emphasizes the use of Linked Data references for annotations.
- **Popularity:** Recogito is popular among some Digital Humanities communities. Throughout this thesis, the number of users who signed up on Recogito went up to 5.000.

After reaching out to scholars with a background on Digital Humanities and digital annotation, Chiara Palladino, Assistant Professor of Classics at Furman University, USA, proposed launching a joint project on this matter. Chiara Palladino teaches Classics with a focus on Digital Humanities and, as a member of the Pelagios Commons, previously conducted research on the use of LOD tools in the classroom.⁴⁰ She motivated a group of undergraduate students at Furman University to participate in the study and managed both study sessions overseas. While I designed this study as a part of this thesis, Chiara Palladino and I currently prepare a forthcoming open publication including the students' annotations as well as notes on the overall feedback.

Notably, Recogito allows researchers to collaborate and annotate resources in a shared workspace. However, collaboration is only supported to the extent that users have to refresh the website in order to see others' changes. Collaboration on Recogito currently lacks the real-time synchronization of data as considered by Dourish and Bellotti (1992) and Schwartz et al. (1998). This leaves room for research on how such real-time capabilities could impact UX. For the matter of this study we focused on the existing modalities of collaboration:

- **Digital workflow:** How do users actually behave when annotating? What are the micro-actions and patterns that emerge when there are no real-time updates? How often do they revisit others' work?
- **Individual experience:** How did participants experience collaboration? How did they perceive the collaboration in a combined online and offline setting?

40. In a course on Classical Archeology, Chiara Palladino conducted an experimental project to learn about the use of LOD collections and an LOD search engine while researching historical Graeco-Roman sites: <https://medium.com/pelagios/linked-open-data-to-navigate-the-past-using-peripleo-in-class-4286b3089bf3>.

In order to learn about these experiences and raise further insights into the more complex aspects of collaboration, we have collected qualitative and quantitative feedback alike, some of which gathered implicitly, some explicitly. First, in order to learn the qualitative aspects of collaboration, we handed out feedback questionnaires to participants asking about their individual experiences using Likert-type and open-ended questions. I will describe these questionnaires in section 3.1 alongside the distinctive framework of this study. Implicit insights were gathered by tracking participants' workflows digitally during study sessions, which provided us with quantitative data on their actual workflows and interactions. The technology behind this approach is outlined in section 3.2. Finally, I will discuss results from explicit questionnaire feedback and learnings from the tracking data in section 3.4.

The explorative nature of this study leaves room for discussion with regard to its reproducibility and the observed effects. In the later chapter 6, I will voice some possible concerns and an outlook to future work.

3.1 Study Framework

The study framework consists of six basic components: three questionnaires (a demographic survey, first post-session survey, and second post-session survey), a self-hosted instance of Recogito, and two distinct study sessions during which participants are asked to collaboratively annotate a source. The questionnaires were inspired by a usability questionnaire design called User Experience Questionnaire, or short UEQ (Laugwitz, Held, and Schrepp 2008). The UEQ framework emphasizes feedback on the ergonomic and hedonic qualities of a piece of software and has been designed to quickly assess experiences of users. In the following, I will discuss the above components in their chronological order.

Prior to admission to the study, each interested participant was asked to submit the initial survey, providing demographic information such as age and education level. Furthermore, this survey posed questions about participants' past habits of annotating digitally as well as on paper and whether they used Recogito before. All surveys of this study have been created on Google Forms⁴¹ and were

41. Google Forms is a free service by Google that allows users to create surveys in their web browsers: <https://www.google.com/forms/about/>. Google Forms surveys can be distributed with each their unique URL and results are stored on Google Drive, Google's cloud file storage.

distributed to participants via email prior to each session.

During two distinct sessions participants were asked to collaboratively annotate resources. Prior to the first session, they have been provided with the URL of the self-hosted Recogito instance and an individual account on this instance. Resources fitting the educational background of the participants were ingested into this Recogito instance and shared with all respective accounts.

Throughout the sessions, all participants were present in the same room with each a computer in front of them, running a web browser that was pointed to said Recogito instance. Each session lasted about 60 minutes, with the supervisors present in the room or remotely via video. During the first ten minutes of a session, the supervisors gave a short introduction on the subject of the session, followed by an opportunity for participants to raise questions. Most notably, in order to ensure the open-ended, creative, and collaborative aspect of this study, supervisors should pose little limitations on the participants' interactions.

After the introduction, participants were asked to start working for about 45 minutes while being monitored by the supervisors. During the first sessions, participants received the task of making themselves comfortable with the given resource and the annotation environment of Recogito. They were instructed to work collaboratively and annotate each resource with textual annotations, given the constraint that one needs to reload Recogito by refreshing the website in order to show others' latest annotations.

Subsequent to the first session, participants were asked to fill out the second questionnaire in regard to their experience of working with Recogito in a collaborative environment. This questionnaire is included in appendix A and asked participants about their work during the session (“Did you interact with others' annotations while working on the document?”) and posed questions on experience-related sentiments as Likert-type questions (“How interactive did the process of annotating collaboratively feel to you?”).

The second session, taking place less shortly first one, was focused on the particular task of georeferencing—i.e., annotating words or areas in a text or image resource, respectively—entities of historic places, such as Athens in Ancient Greece. This task requires to ingest the respective gazetteers⁴² into Recogito prior to the

42. Digital gazetteers can be imported into Recogito: <https://github.com/pelagios/recogito2/wiki/Importing-Gazetteers>. Such gazetteers are digital collections of places, each of which can be referenced as an LOD resource. The import should be scheduled well ahead of the second ses-

session. The selected gazetteer should contain places related to the contents of the selected resources. The session itself has been scheduled similar to the first meeting, with a total duration of 60 minutes including a 15 minutes introduction. This time, participants were explicitly asked to explore the capabilities of georeferencing and were shown the interactive spatial visualization modality of Recogito. Additionally, supervisors suggested the participants to revisit their previous annotations as well as others' annotations, as the group continued to work on the resources they edited during the first session.

The second questionnaire emphasized feedback on the participants' scholarly experience with georeferencing and on some aspects of UX on Recogito. This questionnaire is also included in appendix A. Focusing on georeferencing, the first part of the questionnaire asked participants about their performance on the given tasks throughout the second session and posed questions on georeferencing in particular ("How beneficial was georeferencing places in annotations for your further understanding?"). Given that users have spent two sessions working with Recogito, the second part of the questionnaire asked participants about the ergonomic and hedonic qualities of Recogito as introduced by the UEQ. Likert-type questions asked about participants' feedback on comprehensibility, innovation, attractiveness, pragmatics, clutter, and creativity of Recogito.

3.2 Analyzing Digital Workflows

Participants' actions can be recorded while performing tasks in order to evaluate the *actual* use of a particular tool. Tang (1991) utilized video recordings of joint collaborative tasks during study sessions, but as our setting was designed to be not limiting participants' creativity and the estimated sample size was relatively large—it would have been challenging make out individuals' actions in a group of ten people or more—video recording was not a viable approach for this study. Instead, I opted for the real-time aggregation of particular user interactions. Modeling these interactions during an annotation workflow in Recogito as timestamped atomic actions enabled me to reconstruct individual actions afterwards.

An editing overlay appears above the source when annotating sources, which is pictured in figure 3.2. The derived annotation workflow is visualized in figure 3.1

sion, since the import of large gazetteers will take a while for Recogito to process.

Figure 3.1: Annotation workflow on Recogito. The workflow consists of six actions: initialization (1), creation (2), opening (3), editing (4), closing (5), and deleting (6). While opening or creating will open the annotation editor overlay window, editing, closing, or deleting will close this window and reveal the underlying resource.

Figure 3.2: Annotating classic Greek texts on Recogito. Annotations are distinctively highlighted in the source (a). When clicking on such highlights, an annotation editor overlay appears (b), where users can add, edit, and delete related annotations.

and consists of the following six events:

- **Initialization:** An *init* event is tracked when the annotation environment is initialized, i.e., either when opening a resource in Recogito after selecting it from the overview UI on Recogito or reloading the annotation environment of that resource.
- **Create annotation:** A *create* event is tracked when a user creates a *new* annotation on the current resource.
- **Open annotation:** An *open* event is tracked when a user accesses an *existing*

annotation on the current resource, which will open an editing overlay for that annotation in Recogito (pictured in figure 3.2). This event is tracked independently of who created the annotation.

- **Edit annotation:** An `edit` event is tracked when a user edits an existing annotation independently of its creator. Within the context of Recogito, editing entails either changing the original annotation, adding a subordinate annotation to this annotation, editing a subordinate annotation, or deleting a subordinate annotation.
- **Close annotation:** A `close` event is tracked when a user closes the editing overlay for an annotation.
- **Delete annotation:** A `delete` event is tracked when a user deletes a parent annotation (and thus, any subordinate annotation).

To track these atomic actions, I have adapted Recogito accordingly. As the UI and related components of Recogito are written in JavaScript, I could easily identify the modules that control the annotation editor. By injecting function calls into the respective parts of the code, Recogito would send the tracking events to a backend server via HTTPS. Such an event—depicted in listing 3.1—would include the event type, the acting user’s ID, a timestamp, and the respective annotation to which the event is related. On the server, an HTTP server running in the Node.js runtime received the events and inserted them as JSON-encoded entries into a CouchDB NoSQL database.⁴³ All events would remain in that database for later evaluation.

For evaluating the events, I have used two contemporary approaches on interactive notebooks. The Jupyter⁴⁴ notebook environment with a Node.js-based kernel⁴⁵ allowed the exploration of vast amounts of events recorded during both study sessions. After providing the notebook with a JSON-encoded dump of the CouchDB database used for storing events, it will guide users through preparation and processing of the data and ultimately present key insights into participants’ workflow. With browser-based notebooks on Observable⁴⁶, I then generated visual insights into survey feedback we received from participants by exporting the Google Forms survey feedback into CSV-based data and processing it with

43. <https://couchdb.apache.org/>.

44. <https://jupyter.org/>.

45. The Jupyter notebook environment supports various kernels for running programming languages other than Python. IJavaScript is a kernel for running JavaScript snippets via the Node.js runtime: <https://github.com/n-riesco/ijavascript>.

46. <https://observablehq.com/>.

Listing 3.1 Example JSON-encoded excerpt of a tracking event after querying the CouchDB database. In this event, user1 opens and an annotation created by user2.

```
{
  "_id": "000c6fd0-1530-11ea-8886-214517bdac3a",
  "type": "open",
  "userId": "user1",
  "annotation": {
    "annotation_id": "5c136455-c514-472a-8d33-4756e23b70e9",
    "version_id": "6d693d8e-58a0-4c38-abe0-47a7523003c2",
    "annotates": { ... },
    "contributors": ["user2"],
    "anchor": "tbox:x=2840,y=746,a=0.195281398,l=93,h=-23",
    "last_modified_by": "user2",
    "last_modified_at": "2019-11-15T18:07:45+00:00",
    "bodies": [
      {
        "type": "TRANSCRIPTION",
        "last_modified_by": "user2",
        "last_modified_at": "2019-11-15T18:07:45+00:00",
        "value": "Bandritum"
      }
    ]
  },
  "timestamp": 1575310649165
}
```

D3⁴⁷.

3.3 Setting and Observations

Through her teaching at Furman University, Chiara Palladino recruited a group of students who were interested in participating in the study. They have been offered extra credits on their coursework when participating in both sessions and providing the required feedback. A group of size $n = 11$ students with various backgrounds such as classics, politics, and social sciences signed up for the study. The students had diverse experiences with annotation: All of them were undergradu-

47. D3 is a JavaScript library for manipulating web documents based on data: <https://d3js.org/>. With interactive notebooks on Observable, pre-processed data can be easily visualized using D3.

ate students at Furman University and almost all of them frequently annotated resources by hand. When asked about their use of real-time collaboration software such as Google Docs, a majority stated a frequent use of such software with a varying degree of collaboration. Annotating documents digitally was less common, since just 54.5% of the students stated that they use digital annotation at least infrequently. None of them had any prior experience with Recogito.

During both sessions, the students worked all together in the Common Room of the classics department at Furman University, which is accommodated with a large screen and a table with multiple chairs. Students have been asked to bring their own laptops and install recent versions of the Mozilla Firefox or Google Chrome web browsers to ensure compatibility with Recogito. To guarantee their anonymity while filling out surveys, the students each were asked to pick a unique identifier consisting of alphanumeric characters. Additionally, the students had to sign up for an account on the self-hosted Recogito instance. The account name was asked to match the previously picked identifier. We provided two sources for them to work on during the sessions, both of which they were free to choose from:

- *Catalogue of Ships*⁴⁸: A Greek text passage from Homer's *Iliad*.
- *Tabula Peutingeriana*⁴⁹: A digital reconstruction of an ancient Roman roadmap of the same name. We imported the eleven segments of the map and added them to Recogito as a single collection of images.

For the task of georeferencing, we ingested the Digital Atlas of the Roman Empire (Åhlfeldt 2013) into Recogito, providing students with plenty of historic places for geospatial annotation.

Throughout both sessions, we mostly adhered to the previously detailed study framework. After the students received a basic introduction on their sources and their structure, and a very short tutorial on how to use Recogito, they were told the assignments for each session. During the first session, they were instructed to primarily look for named entities in their sources and transcribe or translate them with appropriate tags, followed by the particular task of georeferencing in the second session. They were supervised by Chiara Palladino on-site and monitored

48. <https://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Perseus%3Atext%3A1999.01.0133%3Abook%3D2%3Acard%3D494>.

49. : <https://www.tabula-peutingeriana.de/>.

by me remotely via video, yet the assignment was intentionally expressed very loose, enabling them to interact within each other and collaboratively explore the modalities of digital annotation. As an immediate reward, we provided everyone with pizza.

3.4 Results

The recorded tracking data showed the patterns after which students collaborated on Recogito. The telemetry system collected 3,029 events throughout both sessions, of which 1,218 events have been recorded during the first and 1,811 events during the second session. They have created an accumulated corpus of 692 annotations on both sources, of which a majority of 559 has been created during the first session. Initializations—i.e., receiving others' latest changes by reloading the website—occurred 166 times during the first session and 74 times during the second one.

Records that are related to digital collaboration, however, indicate significant differences between both sessions: During the first session, no annotations have been edited collaboratively—i.e., created by one user and edited by another—and students viewed others' annotations just 70 times. This changed during the second session, during which students viewed others' annotations 901 times and issued 82 edits on existing annotations. This difference can hint at the use of preexisting annotations during the second run, whereas students initially started their work on an empty workspace during the first session. This disparity could hint at a change in workflows once the shared workspace is filled with content. The students' actions shifted from creating towards editing annotations between both sessions. This shift shows the lack of editable data during the first session, which could hint at prospects for collaborative annotation workflows. Given that changes are transmitted in real-time, users could become aware of others' work and inspect it immediately.

The questionnaires' results hint at positive feedback in regard to collaborative annotation on Recogito, whether collaborating online or offline. Results of experience-related questions are pictured in figure 3.3. While the students were divided into two groups—one working on the Latin map, the other working on the Greek text—I will treat them as a singular group in the following. Except for the difference in group sizes, modalities of text and image annotation on Recogito

Figure 3.3: Results of the feedback questionnaires. Questions on the collaboration experience (Q1-4) have been posed after the first session, while questions on the user experience with Recogito and georeferencing (Q5-11) have been posed after the second session.

are similar and the study setting did not change in any regard.

The second questionnaire asked the students about their experience with collaborative annotation in general. Particularly in an offline setting, participants could feel intimidated by others voicing their ideas—which also counts for online communities—, but the students assured a neutral sentiment between intrusion and overprotection (Q2). They furthermore stated an enthusiastic and energetic environment (Q1 and Q3), which reflects their activity during the first session. Occasional chats of students possibly account for perception of a talkative environment (Q4), as opposed to potential isolation in a remote environment. Despite the previously noted low indicators on digital collaboration during the first session, all students stated that they interacted with others, with 91.7% reading others’ annotations and 25% receiving information from others on annotations created by them.

The third questionnaire yields more profound feedback on the aspects of UX on

Recogito and on the particular task of georeferencing. The students continued their work on the previous session's annotations and about 50% of them stated that they created more than 15 georeferences. However, some students have not been able to reference places due to duplicate or missing locations (e.g., the island of Crete was not included on the gazetteer). Georeferencing has received positive feedback nevertheless, since students found it mostly helpful (Q11) and stated it helped them to understand the source spatially (100%), to understand its sources (81.8%), and even to communicate knowledge with fellow students (54.5%). Reporting on their experiences with using Recogito, they found the UI of Recogito intuitive (Q10) and visually pleasant (Q8) while neither stripped-down nor overcharged (Q6). This feedback aligns with their ability to get to know Recogito quickly during the first session and promptly creating such a large corpus of annotations.

The overall feedback hints at promising outcomes when using Recogito in classrooms. The environment has been evaluated as intuitive and pragmatic, leaving students the possibility to explore sources in a spatial representation with novel modalities for structuring and communicating knowledge. Recogito clearly shows how shared workspaces—whether online or offline—can be used in DH teaching and research for gaining spatial insights into resources by leveraging LOD datasets.

Evaluating the digital records, however, revealed possible improvements on the collaboration capabilities of Recogito. Annotation is a semi-synchronous activity, arguably, due to the fact that it requires focused, solitary insights into the underlying sources. Focus is an important facilitator of the intellectual process while annotating a source. Dourish and Bellotti (1992) anticipate the overhead of *informational awareness* and emphasize a considerate use of communication channels depending on the nature of the workspace, whether conducted privately or shared publicly. The results of this study hint at a two-fold lack of awareness on collaborative operations on Recogito if used in a shared workspace that is used synchronously. First, the workspace *content* is not synchronized in real-time. Second, if changes of others were synchronized during a reload of the website, Recogito lacked emphasizing these activities.

Chapter 4

Peer-to-Peer Annotation

Despite its decentralized nature, resources on the web tend to be centralized on a small number of servers. This development increased even more amidst the rise of Big Data and the ongoing commodification of personal data, threatening data ownership and autonomy on the web. Arguably, academia and particularly Digital Humanities treat the web differently by embracing LD principles and establishing sustainable and self-organized infrastructures. Furthermore, with the Web Annotation specification issued by the W3C, academic annotation services can be provided by interoperable research environments and digital libraries alike. Considering annotation in the current situation, however, poses the following questions: Does annotation belong to the institutional domain? If it does not, how else to store and distribute them other than the web?

In the following, I will argue for the architectural separation between personal annotation and the respective sources based on the assumption that annotations are social data as opposed to public data. Section 4.1 first revisits characteristics of the web. After questioning implications of cloud infrastructure in today's internet services, I will discuss the effects of decentralization in federated networks and P2P systems on digital annotation. P2P systems commonly rely on high-availability infrastructures known as *supernodes* or *mirrors* for replication and indexing. Section 4.2 examines these infrastructures and draws inspiration from public services such as libraries.

In section 4.3, I then define the distinctive terms of *notebooks* and *public entities* for establishing a separation between personal data and public services in P2P networks and the web. Subsequently, in the following chapter 5 I discuss proof-

of-concept designs and implementations on how such a separation can be realized with P2P technology.

4.1 What's (Not) Wrong with Servers?

The web establishes a decentralized network since hypertext systems commonly use a client-server model in order to distribute hypertext documents among a multitude of servers on the network (Berners-Lee 1989; Nelson 1993). This architectural decision brings its benefits and disadvantages. Smaller networks can benefit from this model by scaling easily and distributing resources predictably, yet large networks of world-wide scale can quickly outgrow their intention of being open, accessible, and collaborative, threatening their heterogeneity:

While the Web has the potential to enable full open access to knowledge, the code that powers the Web is not built for that. Instead, the Web uses a centralized data model optimized for use by commercial organizations. In other words, today's Web values the access and voices of people who are valuable to corporate interests. (Robinson et al. 2018, p. 2)

Businesses became increasingly occupied with harvesting personal data, which provides them with a highly-criticized^{50,51} substance for training targeted advertising models and personalization in news feeds (Bucher 2012; Robinson et al. 2018). The commodification of personal data by businesses consequently spoon-fed the progression of Big Data and the partitioning of the web into monolithic data silos (Srnicek 2017). Considering the resulting redistribution of resources on the web in its entirety, this inequality led to a fundamental break with the web's decentralized nature:

While the Web was originally conceived as a decentralised platform where every organisation and individual can participate, it became increasingly centralised with less than 1% of the servers serving more than 99% of the content. (Capadisli et al. 2017, p. 469)

50. <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2019/jul/12/facebook-fine-ftc-privacy-violations>.

51. <https://www.vox.com/2018/4/20/17254312/facebook-shadow-profiles-data-collection-non-users-mark-zuckerberg>.

Arguably, LDP-supporting environments such as Solid and Dokieli attempt to mitigate such developments by emphasizing interoperability via server-to-server communication and open standards for data exchange (Mansour et al. 2016; Capadisli et al. 2017). Based on fundamental web technologies, decentralized protocols like ActivityPub showed that the web can serve for growing autonomous and sustainable communities. Furthermore, publicly shared and semantically enriched data repositories can contribute to the digital commons. In Digital Humanities research, such contributions could arise as digital commentary via Web Annotation and digital gazetteers (Simon et al. 2017).

In this context, a published collection of annotations on a resource could be considered a critical commentary and thus make for a work of its own (Marshall 1997, 1998). Marginal notes often provide context for sophisticated discussion among readers, effectively rendering such annotations social data. Furthermore, as Marshall notes in her 1998 analysis of annotations, there exists a significant difference between annotations that have been made for private purposes and those which were created with public discussion in mind. Similar to a private diary, private annotations are created for private use, and thus personal ownership as well as privacy should be protected.

With *local-first software*, Kleppmann et al. introduce a novel type of application based on established concepts with the aim of retaining personal ownership on data (Kleppmann et al. 2019). Conflict-free Replicated Data Types (CRDTs) are particularly well-suited for use in local-first applications. CRDTs provide strategies for conflict-free merging of changes that emerge from a distributed system with no centralized authority. Under the theoretical assumption of Strong Eventual Consistency (SEC), the retrieval of each separately obtained log of changes will eventually result in the same state across all peers of a system. By furthermore urging for data interoperability and encryption, Kleppmann et al. make local-first applications a promising contender for addressing the web's ownership issues.

Interestingly, the ecosystem of the web is changing. Rooted in the hype for P2P networks from the early 2000s, several protocols for hypermedia data-sharing emerged. Dat⁵² and IPFS,⁵³ both attempt to provide a foundation for redistributing resources on the web. Still, some of their prospects are not fundamentally

52. <https://dat.foundation/>.

53. <https://ipfs.io/>.

new and could actually contribute towards transforming the web to earlier notions of hypertext systems, such as content-addressable storage on Xanadu (Voß 2019). Today's browsers increasingly adopt these maturing protocols with support for Dat and IPFS present in Beaker⁵⁴ and Opera,⁵⁵ respectively.

However, novel systems which build upon these protocols will need to ensure interoperability with the current state of the web. The web offers vast amounts of knowledge, such as publicly accessible PDF documents or semantically-tagged LOD repositories from DH research. It furthermore provides an efficient way for public entities, such as academic institutions and digital libraries, to publish content under their authority. In the following, I attempt to discuss the role of such entities in P2P systems.

4.2 Public Entities in Peer-to-Peer Systems

Supernodes, relays, pubs, pods, gateways, pinning, seeding, mirroring: Many popular decentralized networks leverage infrastructures that provide resources for sustaining the networks' operation. Such services are required, since P2P systems operate differently from established architectures that use the client-server model. These differences can be explained by how resources are distributed among clients and servers on such networks, where servers hold a monopoly on the network's resources while clients request parts of data on demand (Schollmeier 2001). This situation poses several benefits for entities such as businesses and institutions, since they are able to govern the singular source of their services' data by actually *owning* it. Hence, entities can effectively control and guarantee for aspects like data availability and access control.

In P2P systems, this power is distributed among peers. The distinction of clients and servers becomes blurred as the centralization of governance is diminished. Clients become servers while servers become clients, which results in a swarm of equal peers that serve and request data at the same time (Schollmeier 2001). Challenges are posed to P2P systems as they are frequented by people's personal computers, resulting in commodity hardware or even handheld devices joining the network ephemerally. This threatens data availability on P2P systems, since

54. <https://beakerbrowser.com/>.

55. The Opera browser for Android recently introduced support for resolving IPFS URLs: <https://blog.ipfs.io/2020-03-30-ipfs-in-opera-for-android/>.

data vanishes as devices go offline.

Nevertheless, solutions exist to mitigate volatility or low-performance hardware among peers. In order to establish a stable and reliable network communications, nodes can be promoted to *supernodes* based on their available resources, such as computational power, uptime, and network throughput (Guha and Daswani 2005). Such nodes can benefit real-time communication systems with high demands on bandwidth. For file-sharing systems, the replication of archives and the indexing of data becomes highly relevant to ensure data availability and accessibility (Kleppmann et al. 2019). Some of the systems discussed in section 2.4 provide mirroring capabilities which retain original ownership and can guarantee for continuous data availability: Dat and IPFS have *pinning services* (Benet 2014), Secure Scuttlebutt has *pubs* (Tarr et al. 2019), and Solid has *Pods* (Mansour et al. 2016).

Such services may again pose a risk for P2P systems by becoming too critical for the network's operation. The underlying data structures and peer discovery mechanisms can nonetheless ensure that data ownership and autonomy remain intact, even as inequality among peers increases and power shifts towards a small group of powerful peers.

4.3 Distributing Ownership

Although treated equally on a P2P network, peers can vastly differ from each other in terms of their computational power and network resources. I have argued above for the need of supporting infrastructures on P2P networks to compensate low-performing hardware and ephemeral peers. Nodes that establish such infrastructures might be selective in which resources they propagate—e.g., relaying video calls to the university network or replicating an affiliated researcher's archives—yet I assume that they provide these resources to the entire public community of peers. I call such nodes *public entities*, as they effectively serve the public and support sustaining the network's operation.

Such entities can complement the way actual public institutions operate on the web. Digital libraries, for instance, provide collections of resources that are reasonably indexed and accessible via canonical identifiers. The Perseus Digital

Library⁵⁶ and the British Library⁵⁷ offer such collections. By their visitors them with rich annotation environments, high-availability replication, and archiving of their repositories, public entities on a P2P system can offer services for peers as they work on libraries' collections or create works of their own.

Within this ecosystem of distributed networks and the web and public services mediating between them, I introduce *digital notebooks* as collections of personal annotations on a particular source. These notebooks should be considered private and thus their individual ownership should be protected by cryptographic means. Furthermore, notebooks should be kept private from third parties even when sharing them with selected peers—for either display or active collaboration—by leveraging encryption. They should be explicitly versioned to allow for time traveling, and they should furthermore impose an open data model for ensuring interoperability with a variety of applications and systems.

Fulfilling all of these requirements should render digital notebooks compatible with local-first software. In the following chapter 5, I will detail two approaches on designing and implementing systems that incorporate the notions of notebooks and public entities in distributed systems while bridging distributed data into the web.

56. The aforementioned Perseus Digital Library provides a vast amount of classic texts and linguistic data online. The library's Scaife Viewer allows to browse its growing collection of texts available via CTS: <https://scaife.perseus.org/>.

57. The British Library uses the IIIF standard for the offering of some of their digitized items: <https://www.bl.uk/subjects>.

Chapter 5

Implementation

With end-to-end encryption, optional networking, and real-time collaboration, the paradigm of local-first software provides a foundation for establishing private collaboration between peers. While local-first applications can synchronize via arbitrary means of communication, I have argued in the previous chapter 4 in favor of P2P networks. By leveraging direct connections between peers, distributed systems can avoid centralized infrastructures, emphasize local-first data, and thus sustain individual digital ownership. Arguably, local-first software majorly concerns how *applications* maintain and distribute data. An architecture is further required to address the aforementioned questions on *public entities* in distributed systems, which support the systems' operations by providing peers with services such as increased data availability and long-term archiving.

In chapter 3, I have presented how collaboration and LOD can be leveraged in Digital Humanities software. While the results were estimated in an explorative environment, they hint at possible prospects for real-time collaboration in contemporary workflows. By instantly reflecting changes on the underlying shared workspace in the UI, users can promptly interact with others' work.

The use of LOD data sets such as digital gazetteers emphasizes the need for canonical data services. Furthermore, common LD and LDP standards like the Web Annotation protocol specify REST-based APIs for interacting with resources. Hence, in order to ensure interoperability between P2P networks and the web, gateways need to provide additional services for bridging resources between both. While gateways fit into the concept of a *public entity* in a distributed network—as defined in section 4.3—they raise further questions on authoring and ownership as

soon as they relay data beyond the distributed realm. The following section 5.1 builds upon the previous discussion by providing two technological approaches for bridging connections between the P2P network and the web.

Built upon these approaches, I then detail two implementations of P2P systems that provide personal, local-first annotation. First, a system that emphasizes independent authoring of notebooks on the web (section 5.2) by leveraging an HTTP-inspired overlay network protocol and a deep integration into annotation environments. A redesigned system called *Hyperwell* emerged from first design (section 5.3) and introduces institutional gateways that offer data availability, archiving, and interoperability with the web.

5.1 Bridging P2P Networks and the Web

Figure 5.1: Architecture that leverages a gateway server for bridging a P2P system and the web (Matsubara and Miki 2010). For relaying resources between both networks, the gateway acts as both a peer within the P2P network and as a HTTP server. A gateway logic translates between both systems.

P2P systems and client-server architectures operate fundamentally different from each other and commonly utilize different protocols for communication. I have previously proposed the notion of *public entities* on P2P networks for services that support the networks' operations but do not expose themselves as a critical part of the infrastructure. Gateway services—similar to a public entity—can bridge

both P2P systems and the web as we have argued previously in Kabel and Köntges (2020). By joining as both a peer on the P2P network and a HTTP server on the web, a gateway can relay resources between both networks. A translational component then mediates resources and connections as described in a patent from Matsubara and Miki (2010) pictured in figure 5.1. This effectively provides interoperability between both networks and makes resources available to a wider audience of nodes. Further communication technologies such as the WebRTC protocol and overlay networks could pose an alternative to gateways by directly connecting peers and web clients. Nonetheless, these protocols require adoption on both systems and thus demands further technological support from peers.

The Hyperswarm networking stack establishes connections via TCP and uTP (Frazee 2018). Peers discover each other via the Kademlia-based DHT, coordinate themselves in *swarms* (i.e., groups of peers based on a topic), and communicate with each other via duplex streams. Furthermore, Hyperswarm adds additional support for establishing connections behind firewalls (hole punching) and NAT. A proxy server⁵⁸ finally allows to relay Hyperswarm connections to web clients via WebRTC.

The respective approaches on bridging P2P networks and the web will be shaped by further technological constraints. Modern JavaScript is essentially supported in native environments and the web alike, yet both the popular Node.js JavaScript runtime and the web are situated with different requirements. Native environments often require deeper integration with the underlying operating system, thus Node.js supports bindings with binary modules (e.g., C++ libraries) and OS-level APIs such as for networking and file-system access. Hypermerge and its affiliated libraries (Hypercore and Hyperswarm) entail such dependencies for networking purposes or cryptographic methods. Due to these dependencies, web clients can not run the Hypermerge library. This calls for alternative approaches on data exchange when not using gateways for separating both networks.

Based on the above constraints, I have conceived two approaches for bridging P2P networks and the web in regard to sharing Web Annotation resources in real-time:

1. **Overlay networks:** Establish connections directly between peers on the P2P network and web clients. These connections could be established either via WebRTC or with the WebSocket protocol, connecting web clients to nodes

58. <https://github.com/RangerMauve/hyperswarm-web>.

on the Hyperswarm network. Either approach requires proxy servers⁵⁹ to translate the above connection methods to native network connections on Hyperswarm. An overlay network is then used for handling data exchange between web clients and peers.

2. **Gateways:** Enforce a strict separation between both networks by using gateway servers to properly mediate between both realms. The gateway server joins the P2P network like a regular peer and serves an API compliant with the Web Annotation API on the web.

Nevertheless, both the second and third approach promised viable architectures for bridging resources between P2P networks and the web. In preliminary tests, however, I have encountered frequent issues with WebRTC connections due to variations in browser support or challenging network conditions, where WebRTC must rely on additional technologies for establishing connections. Because of these concerns on stability, I have ultimately decided against using WebRTC at all. In the following, I will detail architecture designs and implementations for each approach, embedding them into collaborative environments.

5.2 First Implementation: Thick Peers

The first implementation leverages an overlay network for connecting web clients with peers on the P2P network. By using this overlay network, nodes on both networks can communicate with each other and share resources. Furthermore, by leveraging the paradigm of local-first software, users maintain ownership on their annotations and can—by using CRDTs—collaborate with other peers in real-time without a centralized merging authority.

Peers should additionally be able to author and publish annotations to the web without depending of services such as gateways. This aspect of technological autonomy was influenced by projects such as Dokieli (Capadisli et al. 2017) and *biiif*.⁶⁰ Such software enables using personal storage—data storage providers such as Solid or even storage provided via P2P networks—for publishing and elim-

59. <https://github.com/RangerMauve/hyperswarm-web>.

60. *biiif* is a tool that allows to independently publish IIF manifests: <https://github.com/edsilv/biiif>. By generating a IIF manifest from an image gallery and corresponding metadata based on the file system, users can easily host IIF galleries via P2P file-sharing protocols such as Dat or IPFS.

inate the need for a complex and expensive technical infrastructure. By independently interfacing with the web, each peer has to manage both connections to peers on the P2P network and connections originating from the web. The latter increases the amount of overhead compared to regular peers on the network, thus making them *thick peers*. Within the P2P system, an infrastructure of *public entities* can mirror personal repositories and provide high-availability replication, redundant backups, and increased bandwidth for particular resources.

When approaching this implementation, I focused on building an annotation publishing system for a specific end-to-end annotation workflow. Recogito, the semantic annotation environment used during the study on collaborative workflows in chapter 3, served as a case study during the development. Recogito ensures interoperability with other annotation systems by adopting the Web Annotation data model based on JSON-LD. The conceived workflow considered the following functionalities. The end-to-end workflow included discovery of related notebooks on a source within the UI of Recogito itself as well as real-time collaboration capabilities.

Figure 5.2: Architecture of the thick-peer implementation. Peers can replicate documents directly within the Hyperswarm network (1). On behalf of web clients, the protocol bridge connects with decentralized swarms as an ephemeral peer and establishes a duplex stream tunnel (2). Web clients can then transmit their requests through the bridge via WebSocket connections (3).

These collaborative capabilities build upon the prospects of the Hypermerge library: secure, private, real-time collaboration without the need for centralized services. In the architecture pictured in figure 5.2, users run annotation authoring tools that synchronize changes on annotations in real-time with Hypermerge and join swarms on the Hyperswarm network. By using a specific overlay communication protocol, clients on the web can join related swarms. This is achieved by in-

roducing *protocol bridges* that translate WebSocket connections from web clients into native TCP/uTP-based connections on the Hyperswarm network. By exclusively relaying connections, protocol bridges can ensure the autonomy of peers in the distributed system. Web clients can arbitrarily choose any protocol bridge for connecting to the network, since resources themselves (i.e., annotations) are not stored on the servers running the bridges.

In the following, I will outline two characteristic contributions of this approach. First, a novel, HTTP-inspired protocol that establishes multiplexed request-response communication over duplex stream connections. This protocol leverages the Protocol Buffers standard and is detailed in section 5.2.1. Second, in section 5.2.2 I will describe an approach on facilitated collaboration by publicly announcing annotations on particular sources on the web. Furthermore, by using a further novel protocol for retrieving annotations from a distributed network, browsers need to be provided with libraries to support these protocols. A Software Development Kit (SDK)—a type of library—for integrating client applications is detailed in section 5.2.3.

However, the architecture behind this first implementation beared several fundamental challenges. While an in-depth evaluation of this thesis' contributions will be discussed far later in chapter 6, I will briefly address these challenges in the context of this chapter in section 5.2.4.

5.2.1 Communication Protocol

By connecting to a service that translates WebSocket connections into native TCP/uTP Hyperswarm network connections, web clients can join swarms on the Hyperswarm network and subsequently connect to other peers. This has been achieved by using WebSocket-established duplex streams—i.e., bidirectional streams with read and write permissions—between web clients and the bridging service. By using the `hyperswarm-proxy`⁶¹ library, this duplex stream can then be relayed to peers of the respective network swarm on Hyperswarm.

In section 5.1, I have outlined possible approaches for connecting web clients to the Hyperswarm network. A major limitation of the CRDT-backed Hypermerge library is its incompatibility with the web platform, as it entails native code dependencies. Hence, using WebRTC connections to directly connect web clients to

61. <https://github.com/RangerMauve/hyperswarm-proxy>.

Hyperswarm peers is not a possible solution in this context. However, creating a separate overlay network enabled web clients to communicate with Hyperswarm peers independently of Hypermerge itself.

In order to request and mutate resources on this network, this approach required a separate application protocol. The HTTP protocol meets the needs of this overlay network, as it is the well-established and extensively documented foundation of communication on the web. HTTP furthermore allows for an actual implementation of the Web Annotation protocol between participants of this network. However, I have faced two challenges in that regard. First, there exist no well-established JavaScript-based HTTP parser implementations that could be executed in a web environment⁶². Second, the nature of Hyperswarm connections is not deterministic as peers continuously join and leave a swarm. Hence, connections can not be established on-demand as easily as via DNS-based URLs and should be used as efficiently as possible. HTTP supports to pipeline multiple requests over the same TCP connection, yet it is explicitly being advised against this practice (Fielding et al. 1999, p. 46).

By creating a separate, HTTP-inspired protocol, I could ensure compatibility for exchanging annotations on the overlay network between web clients and Hyperswarm peers. The protocol uses the Protocol Buffers⁶³ scheme in order to express custom protocol messages and events that align with a subset of features of HTTP. Protocol Buffers simplify parsing protocol messages and allow the protocol to multiplex several request-response sequences over the same connection in parallel.

I want to emphasize that this approach of using an HTTP-like protocol threatens the bidirectional nature of a duplex stream as opposed to stream-based replication of Hypercore append-only logs: While the connection itself is bidirectional, the semantics of the protocol are not. A web client selectively requests data from a node, which will make this node become a server. This entails heterogeneities on P2P systems, which I will discuss in section 5.2.4. In the following, I will increasingly refer to peers as clients and servers to highlight their distinctive functions.

Listing 5.1 shows the implementation of the `RequestEvent` message. This message resembles an HTTP request with a request method, a path, and an optional

62. The code of the Node.js runtime's built-in HTTP parser is written in C++: <https://github.com/nodejs/http-parser>.

63. <https://developers.google.com/protocol-buffers/>.

data-carrying body. Other than HTTP, this implementation is a stateful protocol where messages can refer to each other by their unique ID. Additionally to basic HTTP methods such as GET, POST, and PUT, the protocol supports long-running subscriptions which can be opened (SUB) as well as closed (CLOSE) on-demand. Similar to the method of long-polling,⁶⁴ subscriptions demand the server to push new data over the existing connection as changes occur on the resource specified in the initial SUB request.

Listing 5.1 Protocol Buffer code for a request type message, resembling classic HTTP requests. Additional request methods are ‘SUB’ and ‘CLOSE’.

```
enum RequestMethod {
  GET = 1;
  POST = 2;
  PUT = 3;
  DELETE = 4;
  SUB = 5;
  CLOSE = 6;
}

message RequestEvent {
  required RequestMethod method = 1;
  required bytes id = 2;
  required string path = 3;
  optional bytes data = 4;
}
```

5.2.2 Resource Discovery

Several insights in regard to leveraging the prospects of LD emerged from using the Recogito annotation environment during the study of chapter 3. With Linked Data entities available for locally-running client applications, semantic relations can be examined outside of the annotation environment itself. Furthermore, as the UI of an application becomes increasingly lean by decoupling monolithic backends, user-facing functionality can be better integrated with workflows based on the data model itself.

⁶⁴. In contrast to conventional *short-polling*, where clients send requests to servers on demand, *long-polling* requests will hold a client-initiated connection for a longer period of time and expects the server to continuously deliver messages: https://www.hjp.at/doc/rfc/rfc6202.html#sec_2.1.

I have designed a workflow for discovering related work of other users based on the URL of the annotated resource. This approach is inherently decentralized. Each peer maintains its own ephemeral list of addresses resolving to related data. By leveraging the decentralized networking of Hyperswarm akin to the HTTP-inspired communication protocol, peers join a swarm of peers based on a topic. In this case of discovering resources, this topic is a hashed representation of the annotated document's canonical identifier such as CTS URNs or HTTP URLs. Once peers discover and connect to each other, they promptly exchange discovery messages. Such a message is defined more precisely in listing 5.2 as a `DiscoveryEvent` message of type `ANNOUNCE`. Once a peer goes offline, it will broadcast an `UNANNOUNCE` type message.

Listing 5.2 Protocol Buffer schema for a discovery message, announcing or unannouncing the availability of a resource on the emitting peer.

```
enum DiscoveryEventType {
  ANNOUNCE = 1;
  UNANNOUNCE = 2;
}

message DiscoveryEvent {
  required DiscoveryEventType type = 1;
  required bytes id = 2;
  required string url = 3;
}
```

For unique identification, each peer within a discovery swarm assigns itself a UUID upon joining. This identifier corresponds to the `id` field of a `DiscoveryMessage` message. However, this ad-hoc approach for solving decentralized discovery bears challenges on security and privacy, since the origin of the message is currently not verified deterministically.

5.2.3 Software Development Kit

By extending HTTP messages with stateful request identifiers and subscription capabilities, web clients *theoretically* can join the previously described P2P annotation system. By extending the protocol, however, web clients must be supplied with additional software components for supporting the extended protocol and interfacing with the Hyperswarm network via `WebSocket` connections. Software

Development Kits (SDKs) commonly provide such missing components and after equipping Recogito with such an SDK in form of a standalone JavaScript bundle, web clients were finally able to interact with peers on the decentralized network.

Listing 5.3 Example code of using the JavaScript client SDK for interacting with decentralized annotations using a high-level API.

```
const {RequestSwarm, DiscoverySwarm} =
  require('from-me-to-you/browser')
const swarm = new RequestSwarm(docUrl)

swarm.on('ready', async () => {
  const annotations = await swarm.getAnnotations()
  const relatedNotebooks = await swarm.getRelated()

  const subscription = await swarm.getAnnotations({
    subscribe: true
  })
  subscription.on('pub', data => {
    // handle pushed change
  })
})
```

The code in listing 5.3 shows an exemplary usage of the JavaScript SDK for retrieving annotations (`swarm.getAnnotations()`), querying for related work (`swarm.getRelated()`), and subscribing to changes of an annotation (`swarm.getAnnotations()` with a `subscribe` option). For a more complete documentation of the SDK, I refer to the respective code repository (Kabel 2020b). The repository contains an example project that uses the SDK as well as a full documentation of the provided SDK functionality.

5.2.4 Performance Evaluation

The development of a prototype for this architecture coincided with the timeframe of the study described in chapter 3. Having established a testing group, I changed a copy of Recogito to use the aforementioned SDK for storing annotations on the decentralized network. Throughout small-scale local testing with machines on the same network, annotations were successfully transmitted in real-time between two clients running the modified Recogito software. Nevertheless, when the testing group joined from the Furman University network, the machine providing the

annotations from Leipzig via Hyperswarm ceased to function.

The architecture poses a severe conceptual issue: By bridging the web and a P2P network, a multitude of clients on the web gain access resources eventually stored on a small number of peers on the decentralized network, far exceeding their limited resources. Identifying this issue led to significant changes on the architecture, which I will discuss in the following section 5.3. In chapter 6, I will further detail said architectural issues.

5.3 Second Implementation: Hyperwell

The above attempt of implementing a distributed annotation authoring system hinted at prospects for digital annotation with independent publishing and real-time collaboration. However, while P2P systems distribute network requests and computational demands onto a multitude of peers, bridging P2P network and the web can lead to unpredictable and less distributed requests on resources. This increase on connections can essentially put a strain onto a minority of peers. In order to sustainably extend the P2P network into the web, the *translating component* can be externalized in terms of infrastructure and governance. Such components—also called gateways—can translate between both networks and can be scaled independently. This gateway infrastructure provides an essential service to the architecture, but should be of a volatile nature nevertheless.

Figure 5.3: Architecture of Hyperwell: Peers exchange their notebooks in real-time (1). Gateways, governed by institutions, archive selected notebooks and server them to the web (2). Web applications can access annotations via gateways via the Web Annotation protocol (3). These applications can load canonical resources via services such as CTS or IIIF (4) (KaBel and Köntges 2020).

Figure 5.3 illustrates an architecture with a dedicated intermediate layer (Kaßel and Köntges 2020). Situated between the P2P network and the web, the gateway receives connections from both sides and acts as a peer in the decentralized network and as a HTTP server on the web. In the following, I will introduce three components of Hyperwell: The gateway server in section 5.3.1, an experimental annotation environment with real-time collaboration support in section 5.3.2, and progress on a local-first notebook application in section 5.3.3. While the latter is in a preliminary, non-functioning stage as of this writing, I have detailed steps for validating the other components of Hyperwell in appendix B.

5.3.1 Gateway Server

The Hyperwell gateway server manifests the separation of that translating component and represents an institutional entity in a P2P system. In a proof-of-concept implementation, I have outlined how such a gateway could be realized while considering both users' needs as well as institutional requirements. Most fundamentally, the gateway mediates JSON-encoded annotations of the Web Annotation data model between decentralized swarms of Hyperswarm and the web (Sanderson, Ciccarese, and Young 2017). Therefore, it exposes an HTTP API that complies with the REST-based Web Annotation protocol (Sanderson 2017) and complements this API with further capabilities such as subscribing to real-time updates of annotations via WebSocket connections and bulk operations on notebooks.

Primarily, a gateway on Hyperwell provides the following functionalities for peers on the decentralized network:

- **Long-term archiving:** Gateways support associated peers by continuously replicating their repositories for backup and archiving.
- **High availability:** Other than personal devices, gateways can be deployed in data centers with high-bandwidth network connections, 24/7 uptime, and enterprise-grade hardware. These environments can guarantee high availability of repositories.
- **Professional affiliation:** On the web, domains resolved via DNS can express affiliations with an official entity and thus ensure credibility. For example, domains in the context of academia commonly follow schemes such `xyz.edu` or `uni-xyz.de`. Consequently, institutional gateways can assure a

researcher's or repository's affiliation by following these naming schemes with, for example, `gateway.xyz.edu`.

Figure 5.4: Architecture of the Hyperwell gateway server. While real-time replication of repositories occurs via the Hyperswarm network (1), changes are also persisted to disk (2). Hypermerge (3) then uses the Automerge CRDT to merge different versions of a document. The gateway caches recently accessed documents (4) and calculates a sequential change set (5) if sequential updates are requested. Annotation IDs are then translated into LOD IRIs (6) and served via HTTP (7) or WebSocket (8) connections.

Figure 5.4 outlines the components of this gateway implementation. Some components could be adopted from the thick-peer approach. The Hyperwell gateway shares the general concept of distributing annotations via a combination of decentralized networking with Hyperswarm and handling distributed documents with Hypermerge. Nevertheless, introducing an institution as a neutral entity to the system caused additional requirements. I will detail these components in the following.

Notebooks are replicated on the Hyperswarm network via native network connections and subsequently passed to Hypermerge for applying change sets. For bridging the P2P network and the web, the gateway serves both HTTP requests and WebSocket connections by using the Hapi⁶⁵ framework. The HTTP API implements a superset of the Web Annotation protocol by providing the following URL endpoints:

65. Hapi is a production-ready web framework: <https://hapi.dev/>. Hapi is written in JavaScript and runs in the Node.js runtime. With a variety of plugins, its functionality can be extended, for example by adding support for the WebSocket protocol.

`https://www.example.com/annotations/<notebook>`. REST endpoint for operations on entire notebooks. This endpoint supports retrieval of a notebooks' annotations' (GET request of respective pages or inlined container items) and creation new annotations (POST).

`https://www.example.com/annotations/<notebook>/<annotation>`. REST endpoint for operations on a particular annotation within a notebook. This endpoint supports retrieval (GET), editing (PUT), and deletion (DELETE).

`https://www.example.com/annotations/batch/<notebook>`. REST endpoint for batch operations on a notebook. This endpoint supports batch creation (POST), batch edits (PUT), and batch deletions (DELETE).

`https://www.example.com/annotations/subscribe/<notebook>`. WebSocket endpoint for subscribing to changes on a notebook. Upon initiating a connection via the standard WebSocket protocol,⁶⁶ the gateway will emit messages as soon as the respective notebooks receive changes.

The Web Annotation protocol defines a *container* as the cumulative unit of annotations. Containers are commonly used in the context of LDPs⁶⁷ for semantically organizing groups of entities. Translating Linked Data principles to the distributed notebooks, the ID of an LDP container corresponds to the hexadecimal encoding of a document's Hypermerge URL. This hexadecimal encoding is supposed to ensure compliance with the URL scheme. Furthermore, this hexadecimal representation is not intended as a disguise of the underlying URLs and thus reversible, opposed to the results of hashing functions.

Other than the thick-peer approach, gateways in Hyperwell don't necessarily maintain *all* of an affiliated users' notebooks locally. It could extend a smaller institutions' computational resources to replicate all of its affiliated researchers' repositories in their entirety by default. As Hypermerge documents maintain their whole history of changes, they can quickly grow in size. However, in an ideal scenario for the Hyperwell architecture, institutions would indeed replicate a majority of their affiliates' data for ensuring collaboration and productivity. As I have described previously in section 2.4 and section 5.2, mirroring resources for

66. The WebSocket protocol supports the use of specific subprotocols (Fette and Melnikov 2011, p. 12). Frameworks and services can leverage these subprotocols for imposing their own structured communication paradigms. Yet for the sake of simplicity and compatibility, the gateway subscription endpoint purely relies on the WebSocket protocol as a stream for pushing data to clients in real-time.

67. With Linked Data, resources can be grouped into containers: <https://www.w3.org/TR/ldp/#ldpc>. These containers can assort entities semantically.

high availability can be viable for decentralized networks. A trade-off between replication and scalability could either be a selective or a transient approach. While Hypermerge currently lacks a system for managing identities of users, the gateway implementation will instead provision repositories for a limited duration similar to a time-based cache. Thereby, documents will be closed and eventually removed from the gateway’s disk or memory after no requests occurred on the HTTP API after a preset amount of time.

Figure 5.5: Calculating differences between sets by hashing their values. In a simple and commonly shorter representation, complex objects such as JSON dictionaries can be more efficiently compared to each other.

The distribution of real-time updates on Hypermerge documents beared a non-trivial challenge: By design, the Hypermerge API allows components to listen for updates on a document via the `RepoFrontend.watch(callback)` method. However, this event handler will receive the entire state of the changed document rather than just the changes⁶⁸. In the context of subscriptions on real-time changes in notebooks of Hyperwell, this entails sending each subscriber the entire updated notebook instead of just a change set. This practice would put an immense strain on the network bandwidth that quickly scales with the amount of subscribers, the notebook size, and the frequency of changes. Eventually, each subscriber would be required to calculate the differences by themselves. By calculating this change set on the gateway instead, a significantly smaller amount of data will be transmitted on each change. Illustrated in figure 5.5, this change set can be calculated by mapping the value of each item of a notebook—i.e., a Web Annotation JSON object—to a data type that can be compared more efficiently such as a hashed sequence of bytes. Two lists of hashes can then be compared with each other, which will result in a set of added, changed, and deleted items. For hashing, the gateway

⁶⁸. Automerge, the underlying CRDT of Hypermerge, provides a more low-level API that poses little assumption on how exactly changes are transmitted. With the `Automerge.getChanges()` method, change sets between two states can be propagated separately.

implementation currently uses the SHA-256 hashing algorithm, which generates digests of 256 bit size.

When considering data ownership and power structures in the Hyperwell architecture, I want to emphasize that notebooks should not depend on a particular gateway node. When creating an annotation by using a gateway's REST API, it will issue a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID⁶⁹) for the previously undefined ID of this annotation. This ensures that each annotation is uniquely identifiable within a notebook. However, the Web Annotation data model demands that annotations are identified by their host-dependent IRIs. Taking the parent notebook's Hypermerge-issued URL as the annotation's IRI will result in incompatibilities when switching between gateways, as browsers are commonly not able to resolve Hyperwell-issued URLs. Hence, gateways translate between both schemes: Hyperwell internally identifies notebooks by their Hypermerge document URLs (e.g., `hypermerge:/abc123`) and gateways then translate these into IRIs by adding their hostname and the annotation ID to the encoded document URL (e.g., `https://gateway.example.com/annotations/def456/11-22-33`). Either way, peers can switch between gateways by changing the URL host while the notebook ID remains the same.

Some features such as archiving rely on an identity system. While the Hypercore append-only log uses public key encryption for identity and security, Hypermerge currently does not expose such functionalities out-of-the-box. With a focus on Linked Data and web technology, I will discuss this matter in chapter 6.

5.3.2 Support in Annotation Environments

To validate the functionality of the Hyperwell gateway and its compliance with the Web Annotation specification, I have continuously fed the gateway annotation server into existing annotation environments. Due to experience from the user testing study presented in section 3, I initially chose Recogito for evaluating the Hyperwell gateway.

I have been successful in first attempts at realizing such support in Recogito: a base class⁷⁰ called `baseApp` provides the foundation for retrieving and mutating an-

69. <https://www.ietf.org/rfc/rfc4122.txt>.

70. The JavaScript specification gained support for syntactic classes in recent years. While the `baseApp` object in Recogito operates as a class with instance methods and an instance-based

Listing 5.4 Accessing the APIs of a Hyperwell gateway via HTTP and the WebSocket protocol using commonly supported browser APIs in JavaScript such as the `fetch()` method and the `WebSocket` class.

```
const headers = {
  "Accept": "application/ld+json; " +
    'profile="http://www.w3.org/ns/anno.jsonld"'
}
const res = await fetch(
  `https://${host}/annotations/${notebookId}?page=0&iris=0`,
  { headers }
)
const annotations = (await res.json()).items

const ws = new WebSocket(
  `wss://${host}/annotations/subscribe/${notebookId}/`
);
ws.onmessage = (event) => {
  const diff = JSON.parse(event.data);
}
```

notations. Calls to Recogito's own backend API can easily be replaced by HTTP requests to the gateway's REST endpoints for retrieving Web Annotation data, since the gateway abstracts the decentralized network. The compliance with standard web technologies facilitates interoperability with existing annotation environments as opposed to the thick-peer approach, which required further software to support overlay network protocols. After retrieving annotations from the gateway via HTTP, the *initial* state of the annotation editor—i.e., at load time—could be propagated with annotations originating from the decentralized network. Listing 5.4 illustrates how resources can be accessed on a Hyperwell gateway using standard browser APIs.

Supporting WebSocket-based subscriptions from the gateway required adding real-time collaboration support to Recogito by transmitting changes on annotations in real-time and subsequently reflecting these changes in the UI. By utilizing the standard WebSocket protocol without subprotocols, actual connections for exchanging real-time updates can be established. In listing 5.4, the `WebSocket` JavaScript class is used for initiating the connection. However, translating updates into mutations on the browser's DOM challenged this approach. Various

state, JavaScript classes essentially are an abstraction of prototype-based objects: <https://tc39.es/ecma262/#sec-objects>.

components of Recogito such as the annotation editor and the text highlighter are encapsulated and intended to reflect user-issued changes on the annotations instead of changes propagated from the backend.

Hardenberg and Kleppmann elaborate on their approach when evaluating methods for translating frequent backend-propagated changes to a UI. With the approach of Functional Reactive Programming (FRP), the visual rendering of a UI component is considered a deterministic mapping of the components' state to the respective target. Such a target could be DOM nodes. Without any side effects while rendering, the UI will reflect its state exclusively and thus could easily adapt to external changes from parent components or the backend.

Eventually, I ceased work on integrating Hyperwell and Recogito as the aforementioned challenges would have required a significant amount of changes in order to realize real-time collaborative annotation. Dr. Rainer Simon, lead developer of Recogito, extracted Recogito's annotation components into a new library called *RecogitoJS*.⁷¹ This library uses the *React*⁷² framework for displaying an interactive annotation editor on top of the underlying sources.

For testing the real-time collaboration capabilities of Hyperwell, I have utilized RecogitoJS in an experimental but simple annotation environment application (Kaßel 2020a). In this environment, pictured in figure 5.6, users can collaboratively annotate the first chapter of Goethe's *Faust*. Prior to annotating the source, users have to enter the URL of the annotation server. If this URL resolves to a Hyperwell gateway, the environment will establish a WebSocket connection and enable real-time collaboration of the source. Appendix B provides steps for testing the real-time collaborative capabilities of Hyperwell with this annotation environment on a local machine.

5.3.3 Notebook Application

The Hyperwell gateway includes development tools for imitating clients that share notebooks on the network. Inspired by the work of Hardenberg and Kleppmann (2020), I have attempted at building a local-first application called *Notebook* for managing annotations on personal devices. The scope of this thesis

71. <https://github.com/pelagios/recogito-text-js>.

72. React is a popular framework for building interactive web applications: <https://www.reactjs.org/>. Maintained by Facebook, React leverages Functional Reactive Programming (FRP) principles and uses a virtual DOM for only patching changed parts of the user interface.

Figure 5.6: Annotation environment for testing the Hyperwell gateway. Users can collaboratively annotate the first chapter of Goethe’s Faust, as changes on the provided notebook are transmitted in real-time.

did not allow for finishing a minimum viable prototype, yet in the following I will report the application’s technical architecture.

The prototypical Notebook application manifests the local ownership of annotations on a user’s personal device, taking from the metaphor of a physical notebook. By maintaining all annotations locally, the application can provide a variety of services:

- **Management:** The application maintains local copies of entire digital notebooks. Users can choose to create new notebooks or delete existing ones. Furthermore, they can control with whom to share a notebook; this could be private collaboration with selective write access or read-only public access. This choice gives users elaborate control over their data and concerns possible improvements in research data management.
- **Visualization:** Particular properties of the Web Annotation data model—

such as the annotation body or fragment selectors—may depend on the annotation environments used. Nevertheless, the application can visualize commonly used annotation types—e.g., text annotation—and meta information about the annotated sources.

- **Replication:** The application runs a daemon (i.e., a system-managed background process) for the replication of notebooks. Thereby, it provides up-time to the users' repositories and can receive changes made by collaborators in real-time.
- **Search:** Maintaining an entire search index locally provides users with instant results on full-text search of their annotations. By monitoring changes on the users' notebooks, the search index can be incrementally updated as changes occur. Extended search capabilities can analyze semantic LD relations and directly integrate with annotation tools.

Operating systems commonly provide their own frameworks and APIs for developing native applications and user interfaces. On macOS, Apple provides the Swift programming language and the AppKit API,⁷³ while on Windows, Microsoft recommends using the Windows Presentation Foundation⁷⁴ (WPF) environment (among other options). Mobile operating systems, such as Apple's iOS and Google's Android, introduce further frameworks. Building applications that run cross-platform on a multitude of operating systems was challenging due to the variety of hardware and constraints on each operating system. The arrival of web technologies in native software addressed these challenges. React Native,⁷⁵ for example, imposes an abstraction layer between native UI frameworks and application logic by using the React⁷⁶ library for rendering the user interface. React addresses common difficulties when building user interfaces at scale by using a virtual DOM and the XML-based JSX templating language. In React Native, changes propagated on React's virtual DOM component tree are evaluated and subsequently applied to the native UI. The Electron⁷⁷ framework takes

73. <https://developer.apple.com/documentation/appkit>.

74. <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/framework/wpf/>.

75. <http://reactnative.dev/>.

76. React is a popular framework for building interactive web applications: <https://www.reactjs.org/>. Maintained by Facebook, React leverages Functional Reactive Programming (FRP) principles and uses a virtual DOM for only patching changed parts of the user interface.

77. Electron is a framework for building desktop applications with web technologies: <https://www.electronjs.org/>. Electron applications ship their own copy of the Chromium browser as well as the Node.js runtime. They are packed as native executables, can be built cross-platform, and have their application logic written in JavaScript.

a different approach by embedding the Chromium browser’s rendering engine and the Node.js JavaScript runtime into the compiled application bundle. Hence, both application logic and user interface can be developed using common web technologies such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript.

Figure 5.7: Wireframe of the Notebook application UI. Users can manage their collection of notebooks on the left sidebar, while the center area displays information on the selected notebook, its collaborators, and its sources.

Hypermerge and its affiliated modules are implemented in JavaScript and thus require a JavaScript runtime,⁷⁸ which would benefit the Notebook application from using application frameworks such as the above. Furthermore, for rapidly prototyping the Notebook application, either React Native or Electron are suited for abstracting system-level frameworks and thus offering the application on a variety of operating systems, including mobile devices.

The architecture pictured in figure 5.8 reflects this approach. Akin to the gateway architecture, Hypermerge repositories are maintained by a repository manager.

78. While the fundamental modules of the Dat technology stack, such as Hypercore and Hyper-swarm, as well as Automerge and Hypermerge are implemented in JavaScript, there have been recent efforts in porting some systems to native environments using the Rust programming language: <https://github.com/automerger/automerger-rs>, <https://github.com/datrs>. Rust software can interface with JavaScript using the interoperable WebAssembly binary format.

Figure 5.8: Architecture of the Hyperwell notebook application. The decentralized networking capabilities of Hyperswarm (1) and the file system (2) feed into Hypermerge (3) for replicating and persisting distributed documents. Similar to the Hyperwell gateway server, repositories are managed internally (4) and a search index (5) is updated incrementally as changes are propagated. The frontend reflects these (6) by integrating a UI abstraction with reactive state management.

Hypermerge is subsequently fed by the local file system and the decentralized networking stack of Hyperswarm. To provide up-to-date search results, the search index is incrementally updated as Hypermerge propagates changed documents. Finally, the frontend is connected to the underlying data and establishing an abstraction between UI component state and the respective UI framework.

While this Notebook application is an early, non-functional prototype, its architecture could serve as a general framework for local-first software that acts on LD collections. Nevertheless, local-first applications pose novel challenges on usability and UI design, since distributed systems break with the determinism of client-server architectures, which I will further discuss in chapter 6.

Chapter 6

Discussion and Future Work

In the previous chapters, I have detailed the main contributions of this thesis: First, the results of an open-ended user testing study that explored the means of collaborative workflows in DH tools. Second, the design and implementation of two P2P systems for collaborative annotation. These contributions emerged from the initial research questions posed in section 1.2 on the aspects of collaborative workflows and the technical feasibility of local-first software in the context of DH infrastructure. Throughout this thesis I have emphasized possible shortcomings on the study framework and the implementations. The following chapters will iterate over all contributions and discuss them in detail.

6.1 Study and Usability Research

The results of the study presented in chapter 3 indicate the validation of initial assumptions on the prospects of real-time synchronization of collaborative applications. While the approach for tracking participants' atomic actions during sessions featured novel insights into their workflows and usability patterns on *Recogito*, the study design itself has been loose and explorative, which can threaten the reproducibility of its results. In the following, I will address these concerns.

By creating a loose setting, participants could freely explore the means of collaborative annotation on *Recogito*. Nevertheless, given the open-ended environment, this did not allow to articulate specific hypotheses that we could validate. In that regard, students interacted frequently through chatter and physical interactions,

which can distort observations focused purely on online collaboration. Our decision to conduct an explorative study posed a trade-off and required us to provide the participants with a loose environment to explore the sources and annotate “naturally”, as opposed to executing highly specified tasks. We also interacted with them during the sessions, although just briefly. Instead of specifying a strict lab setting, we detailed a study framework and our observations. After all, the results presented in section 3.4 are manifold and fundamentally shaped the design of the subsequent implementations of chapter 5.

Nevertheless, the method of reconstructing participants’ workflows by tracking atomic actions promise further insights into small-scale aspects of digital collaboration. When reconstructing workflows, researchers are able to not only visualize the exact sequence of actions, but also examine the data acted upon. Considering the concept of *shared feedback* by Dourish and Bellotti (1992), this records would allow to validate collaborative workspaces in terms of how users are able to grasp real-time data. Further work on this method could state key insights, such as the average *age* of data (i.e., when it has been last modified) in order to estimate the information flow within such a workspace.

Further work could concern a revised study framework with an emphasis on reproducibility and more specific hypothesis validation. By further isolating participants, less noise could be imposed on the resulting data. This could be achieved by establishing strictly-separated remote settings or simply limiting individual interactions within lab. Furthermore, tasks could be expressed more precisely while still considering the aspects of “natural” annotation. Limiting the sample size per session could finally contribute to reducing noise and overall overhead.

In order to gain more sophisticated insights into the usability aspects of real-time collaboration in relation with P2P systems, further work is required. While research on best-practices of data security and usability of data-based systems was already conducted,^{79,80} there was just few research published on the dedicated topic of P2P usability design and patterns. Kleppmann et al. (2019) provide a valuable set of practices for realizing local-first applications—such as locally available data, security & privacy, and offline capabilities—yet these provide no practical recommendations for professionals in terms of usability and user interface design. Pattern libraries are popular tools among designers and developers alike

79. <https://catalogue.projectsbyif.com/>

80. <https://simplysecure.org/knowledge-base/>

for providing accessible and modular best-practices of user interface and interaction design (Borchers 2000). In forthcoming work, a group of researchers from Simply Secure curate a library⁸¹ of hands-on patterns and metaphors suited for applications that employ protocols and user interfaces with P2P technology.

6.2 Architectural Challenges

The first implementation of chapter 5 leveraged an additional overlay network for connecting clients on the web to peers on the distributed Hyperswarm network. Fundamental issues with the architecture emerged during testing the approach with a small, remote testing group, as I have outlined in section 5.2.4. I will discuss observations on these issues in the following, which effectively initiated work on the second implementation, Hyperwell.

In the context of distributed collaborative annotation, peers on the network are considered to be people's personal devices. These are often running on commodity hardware such as personal computers, tablets, or smartphones. Commodity hardware is commonly limited in terms of computing power compared to professional enterprise servers powering the cloud. Nevertheless, when bridging the web and a P2P network, clients from the web will effectively request data from peers on the P2P network with the expectation of high data availability and low latency. This entails a conflict between the client-server model with distributed systems and will render peers acting as servers on the overlay network. Without additional infrastructures for handling these requests, requests originated from the web will impose a substantial strain on computational resources of peers on the P2P network.

With gateways in Hyperwell, introducing a mandatory intermediate layer between the P2P network and the web helped mitigating possible bottlenecks. Framing this component of the architecture under governance of public entities such as institutions, gateways can be scaled separately from eventual effects on the P2P network. Performance tests on Hyperwell gateways, however, were not conducted during this thesis and are subject to future work, as I will outline in the following.

81. <https://decentpatterns.xyz/>

6.3 Hyperwell, Hyperbetter

The implementations described in chapter 5 are multifaceted and concern autonomy, interoperability, and usability. Hyperwell, which emerged after first attempts at establishing a bridge network between web clients and a P2P network, imposes a separate layer for mediating between both networks. The current ecosystem of Hyperwell includes a gateway server and a prototype annotation environment, with an annotation management application still in development. While Hyperwell proved itself operational during small-scale testing, its components currently lack features imposed by the paradigm of local-first applications. Encryption, privacy, and security are fundamental requirements for private collaboration,

On the question on privacy, the P2P network and the web pose different challenges. When accessing resources on a P2P network, the network should be considered an untrusted environment⁸² as meta information on the requested data is often leaked (Hardenberg and Kleppmann 2020). While Hypermerge and Hypercore increasingly adopt encryption models based on public key encryption, the gateway—acting as an intermediary entity—poses challenges for relaying data without encrypting it. With secure HTTP connections using Transport Layer Security (TLS) for encrypting connections between clients and servers, encryption is still terminated on the gateway. In order to ensure end-to-end encryption for increased privacy, further research will need to be conducted on securely extracting pieces from Hypermerge documents and complementing these with the Web Annotation specification.

The gateway server for Hyperwell has been framed as an *institutional* service, because in the imaginary workflow, institutions would provide services such as archiving or replication to affiliated researchers. The current state of the gateway software, however, does not pose any limitations on requesting Hypermerge documents, making gateways serve any kind of content that is contained in Hypermerge documents. This is due a lack of managing identities, cryptographic keys, and validating requests, which poses critical issues for running such software in public institutions. A further evaluation of Hyperwell in regard to academic workflows should address these concerns.

Finally, Hyperwell was not exposed to any performance testing. The assump-

82. <https://blog.datproject.org/2018/01/16/dat-privacy-models/>.

tion of independently scalable gateway servers on Hyperwell decreases possible strains on the P2P networks, yet the gateway itself was not evaluated for any bottlenecks or performance issues. Subscriptions can require substantial amounts of processing power for frequently calculating change sets. Hence, further work on Hyperwell should address the gateway's performance when relaying change sets for providing its fundamental capability—bridging P2P networks and the web for real-time collaboration.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In this thesis, I have argued that personal data and particularly annotations are not treated accordingly on the web. Local-first applications pose a viable solution for increasing both digital ownership and privacy, effectively facilitating the modalities of private collaboration. This could benefit workflows in Digital Humanities, as scholars commonly annotate varieties of digital sources. An explorative study on the aspects of collaborative annotation in Digital Humanities software hinted at prospects for real-time collaboration capabilities, while it also manifested the need for supporting the web and LOD.

Subsequently, I have conceived two types of architectures for incorporating clients on the web and local-first applications via P2P networks. Both attempts were complemented with implementations, yet the second attempt called Hyperwell proved itself a more stable solution for balancing autonomy on P2P networks and determinism on the web. With some parts of Hyperwell still in the making, future work on Hyperwell could integrate LD infrastructure with P2P technology even more to ensure interoperability with LDPs and applications on the web. For realizing such workflows in the academic context, studies on the usability of P2P applications and collaborative aspects of shared workspaces could further support the development of collaborative, decentralized applications.

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Appendix A

Study Questionnaires

This section contains the three questionnaires as presented in section 3.1: the demographic questionnaire (survey 1), the engagement questionnaire (survey 2), and the experience questionnaire (survey 3). All three questionnaires have been created on Google Forms and were shared with participants digitally.

Collaborative Annotation Study, #1: Demographic Survey

*Required

1. ID *

Please enter the *anonymous* identifier provided to you or picked by you (NOT your real name).

2. Age (years) *

3. Field of Study *

4. Education Level *

Mark only one oval.

Pre-Undergraduate

Undergraduate Student

Graduate Student (Master)

Graduate Student (PhD)

Postgraduate

Other: _____

5. How often do you annotate resources by hand? *

For example, annotating written documents or printed resources, like maps or images.

Mark only one oval.

- Never.
- Very infrequently (months ago).
- From time to time (weeks ago).
- Frequently (days ago).
- Daily.

6. How often do you use digital real-time collaboration tools? *

For example, for writing texts collaboratively (Google Docs, Apple Pages, Overleaf), organization (Trello), or software development (Git).

Mark only one oval.

- Never.
- I use them, but infrequently.
- I use them frequently, but with few collaboration.
- I use them frequently and with much collaboration.

7. How often do you use digital annotation tools? *

For example, for annotating PDF documents (Adobe Acrobat, macOS Preview)

Mark only one oval.

- Never
- I use them, but infrequently.
- I use them frequently, but with few collaboration.
- I use them frequently and with much collaboration.

8. Do you have previous experience in using the Recogito semantic annotation tool?

*

Mark only one oval.

- No, I haven't used it.
- Yes, I have used it once.
- Yes, I use regularly, but with few to no collaboration.
- Yes, I use it regularly and collaborate with others.
- Other: _____

9. Any questions?

Feel free to drop any questions—they'll be addressed publicly before the study starts.

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Google Forms

Collaborative Annotation Study: #2

Engagement Survey

Please fill out this form after submitting the study terms agreement, the demographic survey, and after finishing the first work phase of the study.

***Required**

1. ID *

Please enter the *anonymous* identifier provided to you or chosen by you (NOT your real name).

2. Which resource did you work on during the session? *

Mark only one oval.

Greek text (Catalog of Ships, Iliad)

Latin map (Tabula Peutingeriana)

Collaboration Engagement

3. Did you interact with others' annotations while working on the document? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. If so, how?

Multiple selection possible.

Tick all that apply.

- Read their annotations
- Added information to their annotations
- Received information on my annotations

Other: _____

5. How motivated did you feel working on this resource collaboratively? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Stagnated	<input type="radio"/>	Enthusiastic						

6. How did you perceive your intellectual privacy during the session? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Intruded	<input type="radio"/>	Overprotected						

7. How interactive did the process of annotating collaboratively feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Static	<input type="radio"/>	Energetic						

8. How communicative did the process of annotating collectively with others feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Isolated	<input type="radio"/>	Talkative						

Final Remarks

9. Did you face any technical issues during the session? *

For example, annotations didn't synchronize or resources didn't load.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

10. If so, which issues did you face during the session?

11. Final Remarks

If you have any other questions, remarks, or recommendations, please let us know!

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Google Forms

Collaborative Annotation Study: #3

Experience Survey

Please fill out this form after finishing the second session.

***Required**

1. ID *

Please enter the *anonymous* identifier provided to you or chosen by you (NOT your real name).

2. Which resource did you work on during the session? *

Mark only one oval.

Greek text (Catalog of Ships, Iliad)

Latin map (Tabula Peutingeriana)

Scholarly Experience

Please tell us about your scholarly experience during both sessions.

3. Did annotating the resource digitally improve your understanding of it? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. How many georeferences in annotations did you create/change? *

Tick all that apply.

- None
- 1-5
- 5-10
- 10-15
- More than 15

5. Have you been unable to georeference certain places? *

For example, they didn't exist.

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (please explain below)
- No

6. If so, please describe the issues you've experienced.

7. How beneficial was georeferencing places in annotations for your further understanding? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Worthless	<input type="radio"/>	Greatly helpful						

8. If it was helpful, it benefited...

Tick all that apply.

- understanding the resource syntactically
- grasping a spatial knowledge of the context
- understanding the resource's contents
- providing knowledge to fellow students
- receiving knowledge from fellow students

Other: _____

User Experience

Please tell us about your user experience during both sessions.

9. How comprehensible did you experience the user interface of Recogito? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Complicated	<input type="radio"/>	Intuitive						

10. How innovative did Recogito feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Conservative	<input type="radio"/>	Revolutionary						

11. How attractive did Recogito feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Repulsive	<input type="radio"/>	Pretty						

12. How pragmatic did Recogito feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Inhibiting	<input type="radio"/>	Self-propelling						

13. How cluttered did Recogito feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Minimalist	<input type="radio"/>	Overcharged						

14. How creative did Recogito feel to you? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Fanciless	<input type="radio"/>	Stimulating						

Final Remarks

15. Did you face any technical issues during the session? *

For example, annotations didn't synchronize or resources didn't load.

Mark only one oval.

Yes (please describe below)

No

16. If so, which issues did you face during the session?

17. Final Remarks

If you have any other questions, remarks, or recommendations, please let us know!

Thank you! Please submit your answers below.

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Google Forms

Appendix B

Annotation Environment

In section 5.3.2 I have presented an experimental annotation environment that leverages the real-time collaboration capabilities of Hyperwell on the web. By using the Hyperwell gateway server introduced in section 5.3.1, users can test these capabilities in their web browsers.

The following steps require a macOS operating system. While the software components of Hyperwell could work on Linux machines, I have not tested them in that regard and can not guarantee compatibility with Linux. Furthermore, a total of three terminal sessions are required.

1. Install version 13.6 or newer of the Node.js⁸³ JavaScript runtime.
2. Obtain the code repositories of both the Hyperwell gateway (Kabel 2020b) and the Hyperwell annotation environment (Kabel 2020a). These repositories are archived on Zenodo and on GitHub.⁸⁴ Please use the respective versions of the software to make sure that the following steps will work.
3. Install dependencies via `npm install` on both repositories.
4. Navigate the first terminal to the gateway directory and start a dummy node via `node tools/touch.js`. This script will create a new notebook and subsequently replicate it on the network. Copy the gateway ID of the newly created notebook, which is a sequence of hexadecimal characters.
5. Navigate the second terminal to the gateway directory and start a gateway server via `./bin/server.js`. The server will listen for connections on the local machine (localhost), defaulting to port 3000.

83. <https://nodejs.org/en/>.

84. <https://github.com/hyperwell>.

6. Navigate the third terminal to the annotation environment directory and start the development server via `npm run dev`. The annotation environment will be available on port 5000 by default.
7. Assemble the IRI of the previously created notebook by appending its hexadecimal ID to the base URL of the gateway. In this context, the base URL is `http://localhost:3000/annotations/`.
8. After accessing the annotation environment via `http://localhost:5000/` on a web browser such as Mozilla Firefox, enter the notebook IRI in the upper input field and make sure to check the *Hyperwell Gateway* option for receiving collaborative changes in real-time.
9. By clicking *Load Annotations*, the annotation environment will connect to the gateway server, which again will relay any created annotations to the notebook created in step 4. Users can validate the real-time collaborative capabilities by opening the annotation environments in multiple browser windows on the same machine.

Statement of Authorship

Ich versichere, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und nur unter Verwendung der angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe, insbesondere sind wörtliche oder sinngemäße Zitate als solche gekennzeichnet. Mir ist bekannt, dass Zuwiderhandlung auch nachträglich zur Aberkennung des Abschlusses führen kann. Ich versichere, dass das elektronische Exemplar mit den gedruckten Exemplaren übereinstimmt.

Ort, Datum

Unterschrift